

Evaluation of an Augmented Reality Engine for Head-Mounted Displays

Bachelor Thesis

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Submitted by

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Abbreviations

AR	Augmented Reality
ARWFML	AR Workflow Modeling Language
BPMN	Business Process Model and Notation
DSML	Domain-Specific Modeling Language
DSR	Design Science Research
HMD	Head-Mounted Display
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
MM-AR	Meta-Modeling Platform for Augmented Reality
SDK	Software Development Kit
UML	Unified Modeling Language
VR	Virtual Reality
XML	Extensible Markup Language
XR	Extended Reality

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Chapter 1

Introduction

The field of immersive technologies has undoubtedly experienced significant growth over the past few years. This rise has been led by technological advancements in hardware and massive financial investments by companies like Meta and Apple. Headsets such as the Meta Quest series and the Apple Vision Pro make Extended Reality (XR) more affordable and accessible than ever. Alongside these developments, substantial research efforts have been dedicated to exploring the potentials and applications of immersive technologies. One such project is the Augmented Reality Workflow Modeling Language (ARWFML) which has been implemented in the Meta-Modeling Platform for Augmented Reality (MM-AR). This modeling language and platform form the basis of this work. In the following chapter, challenges in the field and with the current implementation of the MM-AR are outlined and the contribution and scope of the thesis is discussed. From the problem statement we derive research questions to be explored and answered. Finally, the structure of the thesis will be elaborated.

1.1 Problem Statement

Augmented Reality (AR) is a technology that overlays digital information in form of *augmentations* onto the real world, enhancing users' perception and blending the physical and digital realms (Dörner et al., 2022). Even though there is an increased interest in AR during the past few years, the creation of AR software still requires in-depth knowledge in programming and software development. As an alternative, Muff and Fill (2023b) turn to a conceptual modeling approach for the facilitated creation of AR software applications. They propose a "domain-specific visual modeling language for designing AR scenarios, enabling users to define augmentations and AR workflows graphically" (Muff & Fill, 2023a, p. 1). The approach consists of a modeling language (ARWFML), a modeling platform (MM-AR), and an AR engine. The language allows users to model complex AR workflows and has been implemented in the modeling platform, accessible as a web application. Models created in the MM-AR with the ARWFML can be exported and are then used by the engine to dynamically generate AR applications displaying the modeled workflow. The engine is implemented as a web application as well, and runs on AR-capable mobile devices like tablets or smartphones. It is built with the WebXR¹ standard, which allows for web-based Augmented Reality.

¹<https://immersiveweb.dev>

WebXR was chosen because it runs in any compatible browser without relying on additional software, increasing accessibility and making the applications more lightweight. In consequence, WebXR is platform independent. The AR engine implemented by Muff and Fill (2023a) is a prototype and doesn't implement all the functionality envisioned by the ARWFML.

One of the engine's major drawbacks is its inability to be executed on a Head-Mounted Display (HMD), commonly found in consumer headsets like the Meta Quest 3². This limitation is primarily due to technical restrictions of WebXR, as some experimental features essential for the engine's proper operation are not supported on HMDs, but only on hand-held devices. Specifically, the functionality to detect and track images doesn't work. A key component of the ARWFML logic is defining a world origin, which serves as a reference point for positioning all other augmentations within the user's real-world environment. The world origin is established by scanning a printed marker, which cannot be done without image tracking. Since an origin cannot be defined on HMDs, the AR engine cannot run on them.

Other features are only partially implemented. Conditions, which are model elements of the ARWFML, control the progression of the AR workflow. When a condition is met, the next augmentation in the sequence is displayed. Different condition types exist, based on timers, image detection, or user inputs such as clicks or voice commands. The AR engine supports only timer-based and image detection condition types, leaving opportunities for further extension and enhancement.

To offer users a more immersive experience and a broader feature set when executing workflows modeled in the MM-AR, this thesis aims to design and develop a new AR engine prototype compatible with Head-Mounted Displays. The prototype also introduces functionalities not yet implemented in the AR engine developed by Muff and Fill (2023a). To achieve this, alternative implementation approaches are considered. In addition to the WebXR standard, there are numerous tools available for creating AR applications, including development platforms, frameworks, and Software Development Kits (SDKs). Given the similarities between 3D game creation and AR applications, game engines are frequently used in conjunction with AR-specific SDKs. One of the most popular game development platforms that supports AR development extensively is the Unity³ game engine. We will utilize Unity along with an SDK as our software tool and the Meta Quest 3 HMD as the AR device through which users can access the AR engine.

In the scope of this thesis it is not feasible to build an AR engine having a complete feature set as envisioned by the ARWFML. We will therefore focus on developing an experimental prototype with limited functionalities that fulfills the primary goal of being accessible on HMDs. Consequently, emphasis is placed on the planning and design of the engine, which will serve as a foundation for future work. The simplified prototype can then be expanded with additional features and address more requirements.

To summarize, the new AR engine prototype enhances the conceptual modeling approach proposed by Muff and Fill (2023a) by not only adding support for HMDs but also introducing additional features that are not available in the initial engine. The contribution of the thesis also includes, besides the prototype itself, a comprehensive design and requirements specification.

²<https://www.meta.com/quest/quest-3>

³<https://unity.com>

1.2 Research Questions

Research questions are used to guide and focus the research and provide a structured approach. They help clarify what needs to be explored and answered, ensuring the thesis addresses the most important aspects of the topic. During the initial exploration of the field, including the authoring solution proposed by Muff and Fill (2023a) and the resulting problem definition, several key questions emerged. From these, we identified three main research questions that will guide the content of the thesis and the creation of the prototype, and help achieve the overall objectives.

First, it is important to understand the fundamentals of Augmented Reality and gain a broad overview of existing AR technology and research, particularly in the area of dynamic, model-based creation of AR applications. This will be addressed through the following research question:

Research Question 1: What is the state of the art technology for the creation of dynamic, model-based Augmented Reality applications?

Building on the insights gained from the first research question, we will define the requirements for an AR engine and design a new version that builds upon the existing one. The design will incorporate both the state of the art technology identified earlier and the specific needs for executing dynamic, model-based AR workflows, taking into account the work done by Muff and Fill. This leads us to the second research question:

Research Question 2: How can an Augmented Reality engine for the execution of dynamic, model-based Augmented Reality workflows look like?

Finally, after developing an experimental prototype of the AR engine, we will assess it against the requirements established in the second research question. This process will evaluate how well the prototype meets the specified requirements and will also highlight areas for potential improvement. This evaluation will be guided by the following research question:

Research Question 3: How can such an Augmented Reality engine be evaluated?

By addressing these research questions, this thesis aims to provide a thorough investigation into the development and evaluation of an AR engine. The insights gained will be discussed in chapter 8, where the research questions will be revisited.

1.3 Structure

In this chapter 1, a general introduction to the thesis is provided, encompassing the problem statement, research questions, and the overall structure of the thesis.

In chapter 2, the methodologies used in this thesis are explained. The overall approach follows the six activities required for conducting a Design Science Research project.

In chapter 3, the foundational concepts of Augmented Reality and modeling are presented. It also introduces the AR Workflow Modeling Language, including its requirements, specifications, and implementation within the Meta-Modeling Platform for AR.

In chapter 4, an overview of the existing literature and projects related to AR authoring tools and AR engine solutions is given. This chapter examines the state of the art technologies and introduces the existing AR engine accompanying the AR Workflow Modeling Language.

In chapter 5, an outline of the design objectives and requirements for the new AR engine prototype is provided. It specifies the goals and criteria that the engine must meet to fulfill its intended functionality.

In chapter 6, the design and development process of the AR engine prototype is explained. It covers design considerations for software and hardware, introduces the ARGuide use case which demonstrates the engine's capabilities, and provides implementation details. These details include sections on technical limitations, the system architecture, and an explanation of the most important components and classes.

In chapter 7, the functionality of the AR engine prototype is demonstrated and evaluated. The demonstration includes screenshots of the program and covers the menu scenes, origin placement, and workflow execution. The evaluation section assesses how well the prototype meets the established requirements and design objectives. Each requirement and design objective is evaluated individually, followed by a general discussion that summarizes the overall evaluation results and strengths and weaknesses of the prototype.

In chapter 8, a conclusion of the findings is given by discussing the evaluation results and potential areas for further development are provided.

Chapter 2

Methodology

This chapter outlines the methodology used in this work, where we conduct a Design Science Research (DSR) project to address the problem and research questions presented in chapter 1, leading to the creation of a prototype. Design Science Research is introduced as a methodology, with an explanation of the process activities and how we carried them out.

The seven guidelines defined by Hevner et al. (2004) provide a first definition and understanding of the DSR methodology. According to these guidelines, DSR is a paradigm that focuses on the creation of IT artifacts in order to solve important and relevant real-world problems. The objective is to acquire knowledge and develop and implement technology-based solutions (Hevner et al., 2004). Artifacts can be, among other things, models, methods, and instantiations in form of implemented and prototype systems (Hevner et al., 2004). Because it is an iterative and incremental process, the artifact of a DSR project is seldom a complete and finished product (Hevner et al., 2004). This leads to an emphasis on the evaluation of the artifact, which can be used to further develop or improve the achieved solution. It also opens the opportunity to provide feedback regarding the development phase and the quality of the design process. The evaluation not only focuses on the artifact itself, but also on the integration within the information system it is part of (Hevner et al., 2004). Multiple methods exist for evaluating an artifact, with the choice of evaluation methods depending on the specific DSR project and artifact. Furthermore, there is an importance of thoroughness in the methods of all phases of the research and the results of the research must be communicated effectively to appropriate audiences (Hevner et al., 2004).

The objective of this thesis is to solve a problem within the conceptual modeling approach for creating AR applications proposed by Muff and Fill (2023a). Since their current implementation is only accessible on hand-held devices, the artifact developed in this thesis offers an initial solution to this limitation. The solution is a new AR engine that executes workflows modeled in the Meta-Modeling Platform for Augmented Reality and runs on Head-Mounted Displays. As outlined by Hevner et al. (2004), our implementation is not a fully developed product but rather a prototype focused on providing an effective solution to the problem. The resulting AR engine prototype is not a stand-alone software but a component of a larger authoring solution that also includes a modeling language and a modeling platform. Consequently, the evaluation needs to address the entire information system, focusing on the interactions between the engine and the other parts.

Based on the guidelines described by Hevner et al. (2004), Peffers et al. (2007) propose a procedure for conducting DSR projects through six activities carried out in a nominal sequence. A description of this process and how each activity was conducted in this work is provided below.

Problem identification and motivation: Define the specific research problem and justify the value of a solution (Peffers et al., 2007). This activity is carried out in section 1.1, where the problem space is identified and the thesis’s contribution is outlined. The value of the solution is further justified by the literature review in section 4.1, which covers the state of the art regarding model-based authoring solutions, and the presentation and evaluation of the initial AR engine developed by Muff and Fill (2023a) in section 4.2.

The literature review is based on a comprehensive literature analysis done by Muff and Fill (2023b), who identified and classified 201 papers that integrate conceptual modeling with Augmented and Virtual Reality. Using their classification and examining the titles and abstracts, we narrowed the selection to approximately 30 papers relevant to this thesis. These papers focus on AR or VR authoring, domain-specific modeling, or immersive modeling, with seven of them proposing software tools that can be considered as AR engines. For the resulting literature, a backward and forward search was used to identify additional relevant studies and ensure thorough coverage of the topic. In the literature review and search, we did not focus on journal rankings in order to include papers from a range of sources and ensure that all potentially useful contributions were considered.

Definition of the objectives for a solution: Derive the objectives of a solution from the problem definition and knowledge of what is possible and feasible (Peffers et al., 2007). This activity is carried out in section 5.1 and 5.2, where the design objectives and requirements are specified, respectively. Design objectives outline the high-level goals and motivations behind developing a solution, setting the scope for the prototype. They were derived from the problem definition and an understanding of the modeling language (ARWFML), the modeling environment (MM-AR), and the existing AR engine. From these design objectives, more detailed requirements have been specified.

Design and development: Determine the desired functionality of the artifact and then create it (Peffers et al., 2007). This activity is carried out in chapter 6, where the AR engine prototype is implemented. The software design draws on insights from the literature review and the analysis and evaluation of the initial AR engine, incorporating the previously defined design objectives and requirements. Due to uncertainty about the feasibility of converting the current web-based engine to a Unity application in C#, the prototype development follows an experimental prototyping approach inspired by exploratory programming, as defined by Beth Kery and Myers (2017). This method helps to understand technical challenges, test new ideas, and explore different approaches by creating an initial prototype to assess feasibility and design concepts. In practical terms, we applied iterative coding and experimentation to develop the artifact.

Demonstration: Demonstrate the use of the artifact to solve one or more instances of the problem (Peffers et al., 2007). This activity is carried out in chapter 7.1, where the implementation of the AR engine prototype is presented to demonstrate its functionality and capabilities.

Evaluation: Observe and measure how well the artifact supports a solution to the problem, and then either proceed to the communication phase or return to the design and development (Peppers et al., 2007). This activity is carried out in chapter 7.2, where the demonstrated implementation of the AR engine prototype is compared with the requirements and design objectives defined earlier. The evaluation also highlights the strengths and weaknesses of the prototype and identifies areas for improvement. In the scope of this work, only an initial evaluation of the results was conducted.

Communication: Communicate the problem and its importance, the artifact, its utility and novelty, the rigor of its design, and its effectiveness to researchers and other relevant audiences (Peppers et al., 2007). This activity was not carried out in the context of this work and may be the subject matter of future work.

Use of Large Language Models

For both the writing of the thesis and the development of the AR engine prototype, large language models, specifically OpenAI's ChatGPT¹ and Google's Gemini², were selectively used as supportive tools. In the writing process, these models assisted with refining the text (e.g., avoiding word repetition) and checking grammar. In the development process, they provided programming support by generating code snippets, troubleshooting, and aiding in debugging.

¹<https://openai.com/chatgpt>

²<https://gemini.google.com>

Chapter 3

Theoretical Foundations

This chapter gives a brief introduction to theoretical concepts that form the basis of further discussions. We will first explain the foundations of Augmented Reality, where fundamental principles and definitions important to this thesis are explored. Following this, we provide an overview of modeling concepts, particularly metamodeling, and introduce the AR Workflow Modeling Language and its implementation in the Meta-Modeling Platform for Augmented Reality.

3.1 Augmented Reality

3.1.1 Definition

According to the popular definition by Azuma (1997), **Augmented Reality (AR)** can be defined as a technology that enhances or *augments* reality by overlaying it with virtual computer-generated information. The real-world and virtual information can be experienced at the same time. **Virtual Reality (VR)** on the other hand fully immerses the user in a virtual computer-generated environment with the goal to replace reality (Billinghurst et al., 2015). AR and VR can be placed on a continuum that spans between the real environment and the virtual environment, where VR is a fully virtual environment and AR is, depending on the application, somewhere in between the real- and the virtual world (Milgram & Kishino, 1994). The umbrella term **Extended Reality (XR)** encompasses all types of technologies that extend reality in some way, wherever they might fall on the continuum (Dörner et al., 2022). AR and VR are therefore types of XR. In the last few years, the term **Mixed Reality (MR)** has also increasingly been used to describe an additional type of XR. There isn't a clear definition of MR, which becomes apparent in the expert interviews done by Speicher et al. (2019), with some experts even using it as a synonym for AR. In the same paper, others define it as a more advanced iteration of AR, with a sophisticated environmental comprehension and improved interactions. MR has also been used to describe the combination of AR and VR (as depicted in figure 3.1) and as a marketing term for devices that can switch between those (e.g., the Microsoft HoloLens¹ and Meta Quest 3 are both described as Mixed Reality Headsets)(Speicher et al., 2019). To avoid confusion, we abstain from using the term Mixed Reality as much as possible.

¹<https://www.microsoft.com/en/hololens>

Figure 3.1: Different Types of XR (created by the author, based on Speicher et al., 2019). MR is depicted as the intersection between AR and VR, with all three being types of XR.

Azuma (1997) further defines AR as a system that has the following three characteristic features:

1. It combines real and virtual elements.
2. It is interactive in real time.
3. It registers virtual objects in three-dimensional space.

As discussed above, the first characteristic clearly differentiates AR from VR. Following the second point, real time interactivity assumes, that there exists a close-coupled feedback loop between the environmental and human input and the output of the system (Schmalstieg & Höllerer, 2016). The user navigates the AR scene and provides direct input (e.g., controller or voice) or indirect input (e.g., movement or camera feed). The AR system processes the input and responds accordingly by changing the output, providing feedback to the user (e.g., display or haptic). In combination with the second point, the third feature described by Azuma implies a certain immersiveness of the AR environment, as a conventional two-dimensional screen by itself is incapable of displaying virtual objects in the three-dimensional space the user is in. A virtual object behaves to the user like a real object, in the sense that it has a fixed place in reality and doesn't move without user interaction or by changing itself (e.g., by animation)(Dörner et al., 2022). This means, that even when the user changes their perspective and may perceive a different part of the environment, the virtual object stays in place (Dörner et al., 2022).

The definition of Azuma allows AR to be independent of specific technologies. An AR system therefore isn't limited to only using e.g., a tablet as an output device. Furthermore, it isn't bound to visual information and can potentially use all senses in audio, haptic, and even olfactory or gustatory interaction methods (Schmalstieg & Höllerer, 2016). There is also a possibility to augment or substitute missing senses, e.g., providing audio cues to a user with poor vision (Carmigniani & Furht, 2011). For simplicity, we focus on the most used interaction techniques like visual displays, audio, and haptics and will not go into further detail about the others.

3.1.2 Components

The definition above makes it apparent, that a complete Augmented Reality system requires multiple components. On the hardware side there are the different devices like displays and controllers or sensors like cameras and accelerometers (Dörner et al., 2022). These are used to acquire and display data and information and they determine the input and output modalities of the system. To interpret the input and generate

output, a software component for processing is needed (Dörner et al., 2022). Today, most AR applications are built using an AR framework or Software Development Kit (SDK), which have many of the features like computer vision, virtual graphics generation or sensor fusion built in. Figure 3.2 shows the basic process of an AR system with the components needed for input, processing and output.

Another essential part of every AR application is tracking. It spans across hardware and software components and is involved in the input, processing and output subsystems. Below, further detail about the different components is given.

Figure 3.2: AR Process and System Components (created by the author, based on Dörner et al., 2022, pp. 28, 30). The user and AR system interact with each other through input and output, which get processed by a software component.

Visual Display Technologies

Even though specific visual displays for AR and VR have existed since the 1960s (Sutherland, 1968), it was the introduction of the Google Glass² in 2012 that started a new era in AR technology (Berkemeier et al., 2019). In the last decade, many AR and VR devices have been made commercially available with the development following reductions in price and increase in functionality. The goal of any AR and VR device is to provide immersiveness by reducing friction between the user and the experience. We can differentiate between three major types of displays: Head-Mounted Displays (HMD), handheld displays and spatial displays (Carmigniani & Furht, 2011).

A HMD is a device worn on the head with a near-eye display (Schmalstieg & Höllerer, 2016). They can be optical see-through, where the user has a direct view of the real world, but looks through a transparent display where the virtual information is projected onto (Billinghurst et al., 2015). Some well known optical see-through HMDs are the Microsoft HoloLens, the Magic Leap³ and the Google Glass. HMDs can also utilize video see-through technology, in which the real world is captured by video cameras mounted on the front of the HMD and then displayed to the user alongside virtual content on a screen (Carmigniani & Furht, 2011). This is often referred to as passthrough or video-passthrough. These types of devices are commonly

²<https://money.cnn.com/2012/04/04/technology/google-project-glass/index.htm>

³<https://www.magicleap.com>

also employed for VR applications. The most popular video see-through HMDs include the Meta Quest (former Oculus Quest) and Varjo XR⁴ headsets, and the Apple Vision Pro⁵.

For handheld displays, today mostly two device types come into consideration: smartphones and tablet computers. Because of their rapid development and widespread adoption, handheld displays are the most popular platform for AR (Schmalstieg & Höllerer, 2016). They can be held with one or two hands by the user and house an actual display on the front side and one or multiple cameras and other optical sensors on the front and/or back side (Schmalstieg & Höllerer, 2016). They use video see-through, similar to some HMDs, to superimpose virtual information onto the real environment (Carmigniani & Furht, 2011). The difference between smartphones and tablets are mostly hardware based, with smartphones generally being smaller, lighter and less powerful, but having a better camera system than tablets. In consequence, there is a trade off between display size (in favor of tablets) and portability (in favor of smartphones).

In contrast to the other two types, spatial displays don't have to be worn or carried by the user (Carmigniani & Furht, 2011). They instead display virtual information on a screen or directly onto the environment or objects in it with the goal to change the perception of them (Dörner et al., 2022). Technologies used for spatial displays can vary depending on the application. They can be a common monitor or laptop screen in combination with a camera for visual see-through, video-projectors for direct augmentation, or holograms and transparent screens for optical see-through (Carmigniani & Furht, 2011). A typical example is an AR mirror used to virtually try on clothing (Dörner et al., 2022). Using visual see-through, only a display representing the mirror and a camera is needed. The user and environment get captured, the image is mirrored and overlaid with virtual clothes and then displayed to resemble a real mirror (Dörner et al., 2022).

By comparing the three visual display technologies, we can see that each has its own strengths and weaknesses. The choice of which technology to use depends on the specific application and its goals. With spatial displays, the user doesn't need to wear or carry a device and it is more accessible to provide an AR experience for multiple people in the same environment at a time. On the downside, they are often stationary and limited to one specific AR application. Handheld displays are more portable, widespread and flexible regarding usage, but are limited in their processing power and can be, as is with spatial displays, less immersive. HMDs, on the other hand, have the potential to be highly immersive, enabling hands-free interaction and unrestricted movement within the space. As a drawback, HMDs need a dedicated device that has all the technology built in, and the user has to be able to wear it comfortably. The design of HMDs should put an increased focus on visual and wearing comfort, in order to prevent the user to feel unreal, dizzy or nauseous (Yin et al., 2021).

Non-Visual Output

Besides visual displays, other output modalities are used in AR systems, which most of the time only are supplementary to the visual output. The two most widespread are audio and haptic feedback.

Audio or acoustic output can support visual events like selecting objects or navigating a menu with audible feedback (Dörner et al., 2022). Further, it can function as a method of providing additional information or cues to the user by using speech, as for example in an audio-guide (Schmalstieg & Höllerer, 2016). Most AR

⁴<https://varjo.com>

⁵<https://www.apple.com/apple-vision-pro>

displays like phones and HMDs have a form of audio output (e.g., stereo speakers) built in and/or provide connection to external audio devices (e.g., headphones).

Haptic output has the goal to make virtual objects tangible by imitating real world touch interactions with physical objects (Dörner et al., 2022). Or, as with audio output, it can support visual events by providing cues in the form of haptic feedback. This is achieved by vibration, the application of force, or other stimuli (e.g., mechanical or electrical)(Dörner et al., 2022). Examples are tactile gloves or controllers for HMDs with vibration motors like the ones for the Meta Quest 3.

Input and Tracking

Fundamental to any AR application is the continuous input from sensors that enable interaction between the user, the environment, and the AR system. This data is gathered from an assortment of sensors which are mostly integrated into the AR device and can include cameras, microphones, inertial sensors (accelerometer, gyroscope, compass), optical sensors, depth sensors, GPS, and controllers (Dörner et al., 2022). These sensors work together to capture a comprehensive understanding of the user’s movement, position, orientation and surroundings. This tracking of the user’s pose (position and orientation) is essential for anchoring computer-generated information in the real world (Carmigniani & Furht, 2011). It enables the user to freely move and explore their environment while perceiving virtual objects as fixed in place. Further, the user can interact with augmented elements as if they were real tangible objects within their surroundings. Precise tracking is therefore crucial for achieving an immersive AR experience.

Optical tracking, which uses the camera sensors, has become increasingly popular in AR devices (Billinghurst et al., 2015). Besides tracking the user, it is possible to easily recognize and track their surroundings as well. This can be used to identify the room a user is in (e.g., floor and walls), or detect and track individual objects (Dörner et al., 2022). There are marker-based and marker-less optical tracking methods. Markers, similar to QR-codes, are often black and white, easily recognizable by a camera and can be printed out by a standard printer (Schmalstieg & Höllerer, 2016). They can then be put on any object or surface that needs to be recognized and tracked. The pattern and size of markers has to be known in advance in order to configure and synchronize it in software (Dörner et al., 2022). Without markers, optical tracking relies on natural feature recognition, utilizing characteristics present within the natural surroundings (Schmalstieg & Höllerer, 2016). Features of objects can be points, corners, edges or other identifiable points of interest, whose location on the object is stable (Dörner et al., 2022). As soon as different features of the environment or objects are captured, the tracking is similar to using a marker and the pose of the user can be computed (Billinghurst et al., 2015). Marker-less tracking has the advantage of not needing to change or manipulate an environment in order to experience AR in it (Schmalstieg & Höllerer, 2016).

Besides indirect input from various sensors, the user has different means of directly interacting with an AR system. These of course vary from device to device with the most straightforward being the touchscreen on a mobile display or handheld controllers with buttons and joysticks (Dörner et al., 2022). Further possibilities are using voice commands or mapping real objects to the virtual user interface and manipulating the real objects as a form of interaction (Billinghurst et al., 2015). By leveraging the tracking of a user’s hands, eyes and/or body, the user can use gestures and movement to give input to the AR system (Dörner et al., 2022). Examples for hand gestures are touching, pointing, grabbing, pinching fingers together or making a fist. Tracking the eyes allows the user to interact with the virtual interface simply by looking at things.

Many AR devices, especially HMDs, use a multimodal approach for user interaction, where a combination of multiple input modalities is used (e.g., looking at a menu item and pinching fingers to select it).

Software

The software component of any AR application is quite complex and brings with it a number of challenges. These include ensuring real-time performance, merging real and virtual worlds, and adapting to the limitations of different devices, such as mobile or single computer systems (Schmalstieg & Höllerer, 2016). The most important parts of an AR application software are the following:

- Sensor Fusion/Data Processing: connecting and processing data from various sensors.
- Tracking: from the processed data, determining the position and orientation of objects in the real world relative to the device.
- Rendering: generating realistic virtual objects and integrating them seamlessly into the real-world view captured by the device's cameras.

Naturally, there are other software parts that are not specific to AR, like networking and collaboration, or databases (Dörner et al., 2022).

Along with diverse display and device types, AR software also has different target operating systems and platforms. For handheld devices, the most prominent are Apple's iOS and iPadOS and Google's Android. HMDs commonly utilize special platforms like Apple's visionOS and Meta's Horizon OS, or customized versions of popular operating systems such as Microsoft Windows and Android.

3.1.3 AR Authoring

AR authoring deals with the creation and design (behavioral and visual) of AR experiences and applications (Schmalstieg & Höllerer, 2016). Since AR software is complex and elements from multiple domains need to be considered, developing these applications requires the author to possess many individual skills (Dörner et al., 2022). They can be programming, software engineering, real-time computer graphics, image processing, tracking algorithms, 3D modeling, design, and many more (Dörner et al., 2022). To make the creation of AR applications more accessible, numerous development tools have been introduced. These range from low-level software libraries and frameworks, demanding considerable skill from the developer, to stand-alone authoring solutions designed for novice users without any programming ability (Billinghurst et al., 2015). The development tools also differ from each other in terms of their target application platforms and operating systems, which in turn influence supported features of the tool (Billinghurst et al., 2015).

Commercial examples for no- or low-code authoring software (desktop program or web-based) are Zapworks Studio⁶, Snapchat Lens Studio⁷ and Blippbuilder⁸. In chapter 4.1, additional examples from research papers are provided. These types of authoring solutions often employ a what-you-see-is-what-you-get (WYSIWYG) approach for the design and visual process modeling for the behaviour of the application.

⁶<https://zap.works/studio>

⁷<https://ar.snap.com/lens-studio>

⁸<https://www.blippar.com/build-ar>

With more technical and programming knowledge, the use of AR frameworks, Software Development Kits (SDK) and Application Programming Interfaces (API) becomes the standard. There exist numerous such tools, with the most important being Apple’s ARKit⁹, Google’s ARCore¹⁰, Vuforia¹¹, Microsoft’s Mixed Reality Toolkit (MRTK)¹², and the OpenXR standard¹³. ARKit is exclusive to Apple devices, whereas the others provide cross-platform and cross-device support. Additionally, some of these tools complement and work in conjunction with each other, as well as with further ones.

In order to use most of these frameworks, SDKs and APIs, development environments integrate them as plugins or provide API support. Since there are various similarities between the creation of 3D games and AR/VR applications, the use of game engines for AR/VR development has increasingly been prevalent (Dörner et al., 2022). The two most popular game engines are Unity and Unreal Engine¹⁴, with both offering comparable core functionality, tool integration, and hardware support.

As became apparent, there is no universal authoring solution or process that allows for the creation of arbitrary AR applications (Dörner et al., 2022). Hence, development tools must be evaluated and selected individually for each AR application.

3.1.4 AR Engine Definition

We define an AR engine as specialized software designed to generate an AR application from a given input. The input varies depending on the specific implementation and typically includes models describing the behavioral and visual design of the application, which may be provided in various file formats such as XML, JSON, or ZIP archives. The engine utilizes a parser to read the input and translate the information into a format that allows for the generation of an AR application. The output is an AR application that can be executed on the target platform, which is determined by the individual use case.

An AR engine is not a generalized stand-alone software, but rather a second step and component in a bigger system. The first part is a modeling environment or specification, which allows to create the models and files that the AR engine subsequently uses as input. The goal of the whole system is to facilitate AR authoring by using modeling instead of programming to develop AR experiences. The goal of the AR engine is to generate diverse AR applications with varying content and behavior, all derived from similar inputs (similar as in using the same modeling language or specification).

The distinct implementation and features of an AR engine is dependent on the implementation of the modeling component. In chapter 4.1.2, different examples of AR engines from research projects are presented, and in chapter 4.2, the AR engine of the ARWFML is introduced.

⁹<https://developer.apple.com/augmented-reality/arkit>

¹⁰<https://developers.google.com/ar>

¹¹<https://developer.vuforia.com>

¹²<https://learn.microsoft.com/windows/mixed-reality/mrtk-unity/mrtk3-overview>

¹³<https://www.khronos.org/openxr/>

¹⁴<https://www.unrealengine.com>

3.1.5 Application and Use Cases

The recent technological advancements, especially in processing power and mobile computing, have given rise to the research, development, and use of Augmented Reality in many domains. Notable applications can be found in entertainment, education, healthcare, design, and architecture/construction, with a few examples presented below.

An example in education is Quiver¹⁵, which uses AR in handheld devices to turn coloring pages into interactive 3D experiences. PianoVision¹⁶ allows a user to learn piano in AR with a HMD, where notes to be played are visualized on the keys. With hand-tracking, it is even possible to play without a keyboard or piano. In a workplace setting, AR can significantly enhance technical training and tutoring by offering interactive, real-time experiences, such as guiding a trainee in an assembly task (Gavish et al., 2015).

In healthcare, AccuVein¹⁷ created a device that is able to visualize veins on the patient in real-time. For surgeries, HMDs have been used to assist and guide the surgeon by e.g., displaying the underlying anatomy of a patient before an incision is made (Pratt et al., 2018).

For room design and to visualize furniture before buying it, AR applications like Ikea Kreativ¹⁸ are popular.

Many use cases can be found in architecture and construction projects. By overlaying digital models onto real-world environments, architects can improve their design and constructors gain on-site access to detailed plans. This ensures consistency, the correct installation of components and minimizes errors and discrepancies (Kolaei et al., 2022).

3.2 Modeling Concepts

The development of the new AR engine prototype within this thesis is reliant on the specific models it gets from the modeling language and metamodeling platform. To facilitate comprehension of the language and platform, we need to introduce the different concepts and terms in the field of modeling and metamodeling.

3.2.1 Components of Modeling Methods

According to Karagiannis and Kühn (2002), modeling methods consist of two components: a modeling technique, and mechanisms and algorithms. The modeling technique is divided into a modeling language and a modeling procedure. The modeling language is a graphical or textual language and encompasses the parts necessary for describing a model. It is characterized by its syntax, semantics, and notation. The modeling procedure describes the steps involved in utilizing the modeling language to create results, namely, models (Karagiannis & Kühn, 2002). The second component of a modeling method is mechanism and algorithm. Mechanisms enable the usage and evaluation of models built by using the modeling language. Algorithms provide functionality for machine-driven processing of model data, like optimization tasks or simulations (Karagiannis & Kühn, 2002). Figure 3.3 shows the components of modeling methods and how they are connected.

¹⁵<https://quivervision.com>

¹⁶<https://www.pianovision.com>

¹⁷<https://www.accuvein.com>

¹⁸<https://www.ikea.com/ch/en/home-design>

Figure 3.3: Components of Modeling Methods (Karagiannis & Kühn, 2002, p. 3). A modeling method includes a technique, as well as mechanisms and algorithms, each consisting of several subparts.

For a better understanding of the parts of a modeling language, a quick explanation about syntax, semantics, and notation is given here:

The **syntax** of modeling languages defines the elements and rules for creating models, and it is specified by a grammar (Karagiannis & Kühn, 2002). There are two major approaches to describing the syntax of modeling languages: graph grammars (Rozenberg, 1997) and metamodels (Geisler et al., 1998). Unified Modeling Language (UML) class diagrams are commonly used to represent the metamodel of the syntax (Karagiannis & Kühn, 2002).

The **semantics** of a modeling language defines its meaning and consists of two components: the semantic domain and the semantic mapping (Karagiannis & Kühn, 2002). The semantic domain represents the meaning through ontologies, mathematical expressions, and similar constructs. The semantic mapping links the syntactical constructs to their corresponding meanings defined in the semantic domain, often referred to as the "semantic schema" (Karagiannis & Kühn, 2002).

The **notation** of a modeling language refers to its visual representation, specifically how the syntactical elements are displayed in relation to their semantics (Karagiannis & Kühn, 2002). Static approaches define the symbols for these visualizations using pixel-based or vector graphics, but they do not account for the state of the modeling constructs during the modeling process. In contrast, dynamic approaches consider the model state by dividing the notation into a representation part and a control part. The representation part corresponds to the static visualization, while the control part defines rules to query and influence the representation based on the model state (Karagiannis & Kühn, 2002).

Summarized, the syntax defines the elements and attributes of the language, the semantics assigns meaning to these constructs, and the notation specifies their visual representation.

3.2.2 Modeling Hierarchy

Models can be seen as an abstraction of a concrete implementation and are represented by a modeling language. In order to formalize modeling languages, a metamodeling approach is often used (Kern et al., 2011). A metamodel is basically a model of models (Geisler et al., 1998) and it describes the constructs of a modeling language and their relationships, as well as constrains and modeling rules (Stahl et al., 2006). Consequently, a model is an instance of a metamodel, and there exists a 1:n relationship between them. For example, the same metamodel can be implemented using either a graphical or textual syntax (Stahl et al., 2006). A metamodel itself is created and defined using a metamodeling language, which in turn is described by a meta-metamodel (Geisler et al., 1998).

Figure 3.4: Four Layer Metamodel Hierarchy (created by the author, based on Karagiannis and Kühn, 2002, p. 3 and Stahl et al., 2006, p. 86). A model is created with a modeling language, which is defined by a metamodel.

Figure 3.4 illustrates the common four-layer metamodel architecture, highlighting the connections between models and their corresponding modeling languages. At Level 0, we start with the original subject. A model of this subject is created at Level 1 using a modeling language. This modeling language is defined by a metamodel at Level 2. The metamodel itself is created with a metamodeling language, which is defined by a meta-metamodel at Level 3. Each layer defines the structure and rules for the layer directly below it, making a model an indirect representation of the metamodel and the meta-metamodel above it. This hierarchy can, in theory, extend infinitely, with each level providing a framework for the level beneath it. The figure also highlights the distinction between indirect models and direct models, as a model is an indirect model of a metamodel because the metamodel only defines the modeling language used to create the model.

3.2.3 Domain-Specific Modeling

Domain-Specific Modeling (DSM) is primarily recognized as the concept of creating models for a specific problem space or field using a Domain-Specific Modeling Language (DSML) tailored to that context (Stahl et al., 2006). Consequently, a DSML is designed to formally express and model the key aspects of a domain, without covering all its possible contents (Stahl et al., 2006). Unlike traditional modeling languages, which aim to be as generic as possible, DSMLs aim to be as specific as possible (Pohjonen & Kelly, 2002).

In software engineering and development, DSM is used as a methodology to raise the level of abstraction beyond traditional coding by specifying programs directly with domain concepts (Tolvanen & Kelly, 2005). These high-level specifications enable the automated generation of the final product (Tolvanen & Kelly, 2005), which is feasible, because the modeling language and generator are tailored to the specific needs of a single domain, often within just one company (Pohjonen & Kelly, 2002).

3.3 AR Workflow Modeling Language

Muff and Fill (2023a) have proposed a domain-specific visual modeling language for creating AR applications called the AR Workflow Modeling Language (ARWFML). It enables users to design AR scenarios graphically by defining augmentations and AR workflows. Their goal is to facilitate the development of diverse and multifaceted AR software without requiring programming expertise. For the definition of the ARWFML, a metamodel has been created. The metamodel has first been implemented in the metamodeling language of the metamodeling platform ADOxx¹⁹ (Fill & Karagiannis, 2013). The freely available platform facilitates the definition and adaptation of metamodels, which are based on the ADOxx meta-metamodel, as well as the creation of model instances in automatically generated model editors (Muff & Fill, 2023a). In a subsequent step, a new metamodeling platform is being developed that enables 3D modeling by incorporating the third dimension during visual modeling (Muff & Fill, 2021). This Meta-Modeling Platform for Augmented Reality (MM-AR) is currently under further development and is being implemented as a web-application.

As described in chapter 3.1.4, the modeling environment and language are responsible for creating domain-specific models, which the associated AR engine then uses as input to generate AR applications. In order to comprehend the workings of the AR engine, we first need to understand the models themselves, which in turn depend on the implementation of the DSML. In the authoring system proposed by Muff and Fill (2023a), the MM-AR serves as the modeling environment where a specific modeling language for the domain of AR is deployed. The second component of the system is the corresponding AR engine, which will be discussed in chapter 4.2. The following sections present the requirements and specifications of the ARWFML and its implementation in the MM-AR in greater detail.

3.3.1 Requirements

Adopting the process for the development of domain-specific languages proposed by Frank (2013), Muff and Fill (2023a) first determine seven generic requirements (GR₁₋₇) and twelve specific requirements (SR₁₋₁₂). The generic requirements are listed in table 3.1 and show the emphasis on creating an intuitive and accessible modeling language that is adaptable to different levels of detail. Table 3.2 presents the specific requirements, classified into three categories (Muff & Fill, 2023a):

- *Domain* (SR₁₋₆): requirements emerging from the domain of AR applications.
- *Abstraction* (SR₇): a requirement emerging from a general aspect for creating an AR modeling language.

¹⁹<https://www.adoxx.org>

- *Implementation* (SR₈₋₁₂): requirements that must be supported in terms of language specification and implementation.

No.	Generic Requirement
GR ₁	The language should allow the specification of AR applications of various types without programming skills, making AR application development more intuitive and user-friendly than traditional approaches.
GR ₂	The modeling language shall use concepts that a potential user is familiar with, i.e., concepts that are either common in everyday life or related to AR environments.
GR ₃	The modeling language shall contain special constructs that are tailored to the domain of augmented reality. These terms need to be understood in the same way in all situations and by all users.
GR ₄	The constructs of the language should allow modeling at a level of detail sufficient for all foreseeable AR applications.
GR ₅	The language shall provide different levels of abstraction to avoid overloading and thus compromising the proper interpretation of a model.
GR ₆	There shall be a clear association between the language constructs and the constructs of the relevant target representations in the AR application.
GR ₇	In addition, Frank describes the requirement of choosing an appropriate metamodeling language that is consistent with the generic requirements described. This will be considered later for the language specification.

Table 3.1: ARWFML Generic Requirements (Muff & Fill, 2023a, pp. 6, 7)

3.3.2 Specifications

From the generic and specific requirements analyzed above, the modeling language and its concepts are specified in a metamodel. The metamodel does not encompass the design of the graphical notation, which may vary based on the specific implementation of its concrete syntax. The meta-metamodel and the metamodeling language of ADOxx have been used by Muff and Fill (2023a) to create the metamodel shown in figure 3.5.

The ARWFML consists of three modeltypes: *ObjectSpace*, *Statechange*, and *FlowScene*. An *ObjectSpace* defines the real world components of an AR environment (*Detectables*), as well as the virtual elements added to it (*Augmentations*). A *Detectable* can reference the world origin by using the attribute *is_origin*. *Augmentations* have a type, e.g., they can be a 3D object, animation, image, video, or text. *Statechanges* reference *Augmentations* from the *ObjectSpace* model and register any changes on their attributes (e.g., rotation transformation) in a *statechange_list*. A *FlowScene* incorporates the other two modeltypes and defines the workflow of the AR application and how it responds to changing environmental conditions. It contains one *Start*, one *End*, and one *ObjectSpace* instance. The *ObjectSpace* class instance references an instance of the *ObjectSpace* modeltype and inside it, the *FlowScene* model defines a world *Origin* (referencing a *Detectable*), one or multiple *Statechanges*, *Conditions*, and *Resolves*. *Conditions* specify the requirements to trigger the next *Statechange*, or if there are no consecutive *Statechanges*, to trigger *Resolves* instead. Examples for *Conditions* are timers, recognizing *Detectables*, and voice and click inputs. They can also be associated with an *Observer*, which can be used to monitor sensor data or APIs.

	No.	Specific Requirement
Domain	SR ₁	Superimposing virtual objects on the real world (<i>Augmentation</i>) is the main functionality of AR applications. The domain-specific modeling language must allow the user to represent virtual augmentations in various forms such as images, text labels, animations, or 3D objects.
	SR ₂	To create a realistic AR experience, the digital augmentations superimposed on the physical world must align with the real world. A virtual augmentation placed on a real object should remain in its original position relative to the real object, even as the user moves around. Therefore, the modeling language must provide a concept for creating a local real-world origin to provide a reference point at application runtime (<i>World Origin Reference</i>).
	SR ₃	It must be possible to specify the location of virtual augmentations in relation to other objects or the world origin in real or virtual space during model specification (<i>Reference Point</i>).
	SR ₄	It must be possible to specify real-world objects that can be tracked during application runtime (<i>Detectable/Trackable</i>). Therefore, a concept is required to create such detectable objects during modeling. These detectables should not only specify the existence of a real-world object, but also provide data to recognize these objects at runtime, for example using images or 3D object data.
	SR ₅	Specifying the modification of different objects based on different <i>actions</i> is a critical functionality of AR applications. Thus, the modeling language should permit to define transitions to subsequent actions and to directly manipulate and transform augmentations.
	SR ₆	For realizing complex AR workflows, <i>triggers and conditions</i> are required to enable dynamic branchings in AR applications.
Abstract.	SR ₇	To reduce complexity and to separate the different roles required during the specification of AR scenarios, the modeling language shall include concepts for abstraction, e.g., model decomposition, and separation of concerns to allow task sharing among stakeholders with different responsibilities.
Implementation	SR ₈	Due to the nature of modeling languages, an abstract and a concrete syntax in textual notation needs to be provided, also for easing future interoperability with previous approaches. In addition, as visual notations are more intuitive and user-friendly than text-based notations, a two-dimensional graphical notation needs to be specified. Finally, since the AR domain reverts largely to 3D content, specifying models directly in a 3D environment is useful to facilitate spatial imagination. Thus, a domain-specific modeling language should consider concepts for text-based, 2D visual, and 3D spatial modeling.
	SR ₉	To allow for an easy and rapid adaptation of the language as requirements change, the modeling language shall be based on <i>metamodeling</i> .
	SR ₁₀	It should be possible to directly feed the model into an AR application for the <i>execution</i> of the modeled AR scenario. Thus, a domain-specific modeling language for AR applications shall provide a data format that can be processed by an AR engine during runtime or generate code for creating the AR application itself from the models.
	SR ₁₁	AR applications are often built using commercial SDKs such as Apple ARKit, Wikitude, or Vuforia, most of which depend on the closed-source Unity development platform. To make the modeling language widely applicable on a large range of devices and enable non-commercial long-term research, the modeling language (<i>specification</i>) and code generated from it (<i>execution</i>) shall be based on open standards, such as the WebXR Device API.
	SR ₁₂	To ensure reproducibility and accessibility, the implementation of the domain-specific modeling language shall be made openly available.

Table 3.2: ARWFML Specific Requirements (Muff & Fill, 2023a, pp. 7, 8)

3.3.3 Implementation in the Meta-Modeling Platform for AR

The first implementation of the ARWFML with a specified graphical notation was made in the ADOxx metamodeling platform and is described by Muff and Fill (2023a). It is available via Zenodo²⁰. Currently under development is a web-based modeling platform called the Meta-Modeling Platform for Augmented Reality (MM-AR). It will be presented in a future research paper by Muff and Fill. The new platform is a complete modeling environment, which uses the same metamodel (figure 3.5), but has a different graphical notation. In contrast to the majority of visual modeling tools that only work on a 2D canvas, the MM-AR is based on a 3D environment, enabling modeling both in 2D and 3D (Muff & Fill, 2021). Additionally, since it is a metamodeling platform, it not only supports the ARWFML, but also other modeling languages that can be imported via their metamodels.

The prototype of the MM-AR is being developed with the programming language JavaScript and the Three.js library²¹. Three.js is a JavaScript library for creating and displaying animated 3D content in web browsers and it enables the 3D modeling feature of the MM-AR. *ObjectSpace*, *Statechange*, and *FlowScene* models created with the ARWFML can be exported and saved in a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) file. To achieve this, the MM-AR converts the modeled visual information, specifying augmentations or workflows, to a textual JSON format. Data regarding the virtual augmentation objects can be geometrical (e.g., coordinates and rotation), graphical (e.g., texture and visibility), or describing other attributes (e.g., augmentation type and *is_origin*). The workflow in the *FlowScene* model includes data about the modeled instances (e.g., *ObjectSpace*, *Statechanges*, and *Conditions*), and, most importantly, how they are interconnected. All of this information regarding the class instances and their relationships is stored in the JSON file. Each model of the three modeltypes is saved separately and will subsequently be imported by the AR engine to generate the AR application.

3.3.4 Example in the Meta-Modeling Platform for AR

We will now take a look at the MM-AR and the concrete syntax of the ARWFML with an example. The Lego example was modeled by Muff and encompasses a simple AR application showing the building of a Lego tower using three blocks with different colors (green, blue, and red). Between each placement, there is a pause of a few seconds. Figure 3.6 presents the modeled *ObjectSpace* in the MM-AR. The modeling space is in the middle, modeling elements on the left side, element details and attributes on the right side, and other tools of the platform (e.g., import/export models, and toggle between 2D and 3D) at the top. The Lego example has three *Augmentations*, one for each block, and one *Detectable* which references the world origin. The *Detectable* contains an image of a marker and must be printed in a specific size. It determines the origin of the AR application upon scanning it with the AR device. Figure 3.7 shows the three *Statechanges* needed, each modeled in a separate file. The *Augmentations* from the *ObjectSpace* are referenced and used to incrementally build the tower with each *Statechange*, defining the state of the position, rotation, and visibility parameters. The workflow of the AR application is modeled in the *FlowScene* visible in figure 3.8. It incorporates one *ObjectSpace* model and multiple *Statechange* models. The *Origin* references the

²⁰<https://zenodo.org/records/8207639>

²¹<https://threejs.org>

Detectable and starts the *trigger-condition-action* sequences following it. The *Conditions* are all timers of different lengths, pausing the application e.g., for five seconds between "Statechange 1" and "Statechange 2". In figure 3.9, the "Statechange 3" model is shown with 3D mode enabled, demonstrating the three-dimensional modeling feature of the MM-AR. While this simple example doesn't gain much from 3D modeling, the feature becomes very useful in more complex applications.

Figure 3.6: MM-AR *ObjectSpace*: Lego Example (modeled by Muff). Screenshot of the MM-AR modeling environment showing an *ObjectSpace* model, which encompasses three *Augmentations* and one *Observable* marker.

Figure 3.7: MM-AR *Statechange*: Lego Example (modeled by Muff). Screenshot of the three *Statechange* models, which reference the *Augmentations* of the *ObjectSpace* instance.

The *ObjectSpace*, *Statechange*, and *FlowScene* models can subsequently be converted to JSON files. Figure 3.10 presents the JSON file that gets created by the MM-AR when exporting the *FlowScene* model from figure 3.8. Only the top-level view is visible, illustrating the general structure of how these models are saved in text format. We can see stored geometrical data, such as 2D and 3D coordinates, and general information like a name, IDs, and custom variables. The two most important fields are the "class_instances" and the "relationclasses_instances", both of which contain a list. "class_instances" enumerates all class

Figure 3.8: MM-AR *FlowScene*: Lego Example (modeled by Muff). Screenshot of the *FlowScene* model showing the workflow of the application. It references the *ObjectSpace* and *Statechanges*, and uses *Start*, *Origin*, *Condition*, *Exit*, and *End* instances.

Figure 3.9: MM-AR 3D *Statechange*: Lego Example (modeled by Muff). Screenshot of the "Statechange 3" model in 3D mode, demonstrating the three-dimensional modeling capability of the MM-AR.

```

1  {
2    "38c4b17f-811c-4ef3-a41e-32840ebd9ff0": {
3      "uuid": "38c4b17f-811c-4ef3-a41e-32840ebd9ff0",
4    > "coordinates_2d": {--
8      },
9    > "relative_coordinate_3d": {--
13     },
14  > "rotation": {--
19     },
20     "custom_variables": {},
21     "uuid_scene_type": "9c71b8fd-c31e-447f-b617-77af5e33f7da",
22  > "class_instances": [--
2007  ],
2008  "role_instances": [],
2009  "attribute_instances": [],
2010  "port_instances": [],
2011 > "relationclasses_instances": [--
3642  ],
3643  "creation_time": "2023-10-11T07:18:37.139Z",
3644  "modification_time": "2023-10-12T15:26:09.321Z",
3645  "geometry": null,
3646  "absolute_coordinate_3d": null,
3647  "visibility": null,
3648  "name": "Lego Example FlowScene",
3649  "description": null,
3650  "uuid_instance_object": "38c4b17f-811c-4ef3-a41e-32840ebd9ff0",
3651  "selected": true
3652  }
3653 }

```

Figure 3.10: MM-AR JSON of *FlowScene*: Lego Example (modeled by Muff). Screenshot of the JSON file that gets created when exporting the *FlowScene* model.

elements present in this model along with their individual details (coordinates, rotation, attributes, ID, etc.). This specific *FlowScene* has the following class instances: *Start*, *End*, *Origin*, *Exit*, *ObjectSpace*, three *Statechanges*, and four *Conditions*. "relationclasses_instances" describe the relationships between the class instances, represented by connecting arrows. The relationclasses can be of different types, which are: *starts* (connecting *Start* to *Origin*), *has_condition* (arrows going to *Conditions*), *triggers* (arrows coming from *Conditions*), *ends* (connecting *Exit* to *End*), and *has_observer* (not present in this example). Each relationclass also has individual information such as the class instances it connects, coordinates, type, ID, and other relevant data.

This file, along with the JSON files from the other models, serves as the input for the current AR engine created by Muff and Fill (2023a), and later for the new AR engine prototype developed as part of this thesis.

Chapter 4

Related Work

There exist numerous research projects and literature in the field of Augmented Reality. This chapter provides a brief overview of relevant projects that mostly focus on the development and creation of AR applications in a model-driven approach. This thesis concentrates on the software component responsible for dynamically translating models into AR applications, which we call the AR engine. Therefore, our primary focus is not on the modeling, but on the AR engine component of each research project. This chapter aims to answer the first research question of this thesis.

In the first part of this chapter, we will review state of the art solutions and gain an understanding of current implementations and technologies used. Then, we analyse the AR engine which was developed by Muff and Fill (2023a) alongside the ARWFML and the MM-AR.

4.1 State of the Art

The research relating the state of the art is based on a comprehensive literature analysis done by Muff and Fill (2023b), where they identified papers that intersect Augmented Reality or Virtual Reality with conceptual modeling. We looked at the 201 papers they found and selected the projects most relevant to this thesis. The resulting chosen literature consists of over 30 papers that have a focus on AR/VR authoring, domain-specific modeling, or immersive modeling (modeling inside an AR/VR environment). Below, we outline the most important of these projects with the goal to get a general overview of the topic and technologies used. Afterwards, we put a focus on papers which, besides their authoring or modeling solution, propose a tool that can be described as an AR/VR engine.

4.1.1 AR Authoring Tools

Engelke et al. (2013) created an authoring system that allows the transfer of traditional maintenance task descriptions to an AR application. In a JSON file, the instructions and the declarative structure are saved, which then defines the content of the user interface. They put a focus on using tablets as AR devices. The software implementation is done with the instantAR framework, which creates a web-kit based browser application (Engelke et al., 2013).

With a *Contextual Augmented Reality Language (CARL)* and *Contextual Augmented Reality Environments*

(*CARE*), Rumiński and Walczak (2014a) propose a method of modeling dynamic, contextual and interactive AR environments. Their approach allows for the selection of real-world objects to augment and the content of augmentation. This selection is determined by factors such as user location, privileges, and device capabilities. The AR content is described in a *CARE* environment and then encoded in the *Contextual Augmented Reality Language (CARL)* and sent to a generic *CARL* browser application. The application will then execute the AR presentation and show the relevant contextual AR content. It has been built in Java for Android and uses the Vuforia development kit for tracking (Rumiński & Walczak, 2014a, 2014b; Walczak et al., 2014).

Geng et al. (2020) propose a design method of adaptive Augmented Reality Work Instructions (ARWI) that isn't reliant on programming. They focus on complex industrial operations. The process works by creating a template document that can be complemented with real-world AR content. On-site operators use this skeleton to conduct trial operations step by step in the actual environment. They record each step and create AR content, eventually completing the full ARWI. The production operator then carries out the operation using the completed ARWI. The use case implementation is done in Unity and uses EasyAR for environment tracking. XML format is used for the storage of the ARWI. For hardware, the TechLens T2 smart glasses have been chosen as a HMD (Geng et al., 2020).

Van Lopik et al. (2020) created an AR authoring application that enables shop floor AR content creation. It works by capturing actions of a task expert with a HMD in audio and video format. The step by step instructions can then be viewed and followed on a Microsoft HoloLens HMD. Their implementation uses Unity and the Mixed Reality Toolkit where the instructional images and videos are directly added to the Unity project. They however propose an extension of their solution with a web application that can be used for managing and editing the content. Additional to the web interface is a back end that converts and adds the content to the AR application template and deploys it to the HMD (Van Lopik et al., 2020).

Ruiz-Rube et al. (2020) present a framework to systematically develop AR editors for Domain Specific Languages (DSL). The design of the AR editors is based on a metamodel. For the implementation of the tools they considered two strategies: 1. Creating an AR engine application capable of interpreting any model definition from an AR-based editor; 2. Establishing a shared codebase and employing a preliminary code generation process to generate language-specific code. The second option was chosen and a generic mobile Android modeling application developed. The base application is extended with DSL-specific implementations and together they are compiled and built into the target platform. The application is developed in Unity and uses the Vuforia development kit for tracking. For the modeling of the editors, Eclipse IDE plug-ins have been implemented. There are no details given on the specific hardware used (Ruiz-Rube et al., 2020).

With *ProcessAR*, Chidambaram et al. (2021) created an AR authoring system, which allows knowledge transfer from a domain expert to a novice. They focus on spatio-temporal tasks like assembling an engine or repairing a bike. The expert records their movements, tool-usage and vocal instructions with a headset to create a 3D tutorial. The novice then watches the overlaid tutorial and completes checkpoints in order to finish the tasks. For the implementation they used an Oculus Rift HMD with an extra camera attached to the headset which enables passthrough and object detection. On the software side, Unity and the Unity Oculus SDK was chosen (Chidambaram et al., 2021).

Esengün et al. (2023) focus on the creation of an AR process management system for industrial environments. The system is based on a client-server architecture and is composed of two parts. First, a web-interface that is used for managing processes and authoring AR content. Second, a mobile AR application that executes the created processes and shows the AR content. Depending on the definitions in the web-interface, the UI of the mobile application can change, which makes it dynamic. The implementation of the mobile application is based on Unity and uses the Vuforia SDK to realize marker-based AR. It is cross-platform and works on Android and iOS devices like smartphones and tables, as well as the Microsoft HoloLens 1 HMD (Esengün et al., 2023).

Reviewing these papers and their implementation details reveals that the proposed AR authoring solutions are not only made for specific application scenarios but also rely on distinct hardware and software technologies. These systems vary depending on their target environments, devices, and objectives, from industrial operations and maintenance tasks to domain-specific modeling and knowledge transfer. Each approach utilizes a different combination of development platforms, programming languages, software tools, and devices. The choice of technologies depends on the specific requirements of each solution, highlighting that they must be selected on a case-by-case basis.

4.1.2 AR Engine Solutions

Now we will take a look at projects proposing something similar to our definition of an AR engine. In order to get a good overview, the following papers present different approaches and implementations done recently and in the past.

Haringer and Regenbrecht (2002) describe an AR authoring system used for building AR-based manuals. It has two main components: an AR editor and an AR viewer. The editor uses Microsoft PowerPoint slides as a basis to which 3D content, spatial arrangement and other specifications are added. The enriched presentation is exported into an XML file. The viewer opens and parses the XML into a Document Object Model (DOM) which in turn is used to generate a UML diagram. From the UML diagram the presentation is converted into 3D space that can be viewed on a desktop screen or in AR and VR on a HMD. There is no further detail given on the specific devices or software technologies used in the implementation (Haringer & Regenbrecht, 2002).

The AR viewer of the authoring system can be described as an AR engine, which takes an XML file and generates an AR manual presentation.

Vitzthum (2006) proposes a visual modeling language based on UML in order to create AR user interfaces. For the specification of these interfaces, he uses the Scene Structure and Integration Modeling Language with an extension for AR (SSIML/AR). Models created with SSIML/AR reflect the structure of AR user interfaces and are converted to XML Model Interchange (XMI)-format. The modeling is therefore not dependent on a specific target language and platform. For the implementation of a use case, a framework has been developed to automatically generate Java code from the XMI-encoded models. The framework consists of subsystems handling e.g., the tracking, input or contextual aspects. Since the generated code is incomplete, a developer has to fill in the missing parts by hand and the AR application can then be compiled to a target device. The

JARToolkit and Java3D were used for the implementation of the framework (Vitzthum, 2006).

The described framework is an (incomplete) AR engine, that takes an XMI-encoded SSIML/AR model and generates platform specific code. It is not a full AR engine, because a developer still has to supplement and finalize the application.

Gimeno et al. (2013) introduce an AR authoring tool tailored for creating AR applications designed specifically to facilitate the execution of industrial sequential procedures. Their framework consists of two separate applications: an AR editor and an AR viewer. The editor allows users without programming knowledge to create AR procedures based on steps. A procedure and the corresponding multimedia contents are then saved in XML format in a custom zip-compressed archive defining the AR application. This archive is imported, analysed and the application executed by the viewer, which allows the user-created procedure to be shown. The AR viewer was developed on C++, uses the OpenSceneGraph framework and runs on Symbian, iOS and Android devices. In order to enable the configuration of occlusion capabilities, a Kinect sensor that captures depth information has been used. Another feature is tracking by the use of markers, which relies on ARToolKitPlus and Vuforia (Gimeno et al., 2013).

The AR viewer of the framework is an AR engine, that extracts the files from the archive, interprets and processes them, and generates an AR application that shows the user-created procedure.

With *UBBA*, Abdul et al. (2019) created a *Unity Based BPMN Animator* that builds a 3D virtual world from a Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) diagram. Their project doesn't use AR or VR for the execution of the animation and instead displays the resulting 3D space on a desktop screen. *UBBA* works with any standard *.bpmn* file in XML format. The process consists of parsing the file, assigning a graphic to each diagram element and displaying the resulting 3D scene. To read the BPMN file, they implemented a parser, which generates a custom data structure from the input file. Using the parsed model, *UBBA* gathers details about the diagram's elements, like their name, type, and position in the 2D plane. This information is then utilized by the tool to configure the 3D space. For each identified element, *UBBA* enables the association of a 3D graphic, providing the designer with the option to either load graphics from their PC or select from those already available in *UBBA*. Finally, the model as a resulting 3D space is shown and the diagram execution in form of token movements can be animated. The implementation was created with Unity (Abdul et al., 2019).

UBBA can therefore be described as a 3D engine, that takes a *.bpmn* diagram file and graphics as input and transforms these into a 3D visualization and animation. It is not dissimilar to an AR engine, which, instead of creating a 3D space, generates an AR application.

Thies et al. (2019) focus on the generation of AR and VR training applications from Business Process Models (BPM). Their approach revolves around a custom compiler and application framework that converts these process models and a corresponding machine model into a ready-to-run AR/VR application. The training tasks are modeled as a workflow in a BPM and the machine model, consisting of a CAD model and further specifications, describes all feasible interactions with the machine. The compiler essentially is a parser, that traverses the entire BPM, links it with the machine model and translates this input to an abstract graph. The application framework has the abstract graph as an input and creates from it an AR/VR training application, which itself is a large state machine. Both the compiler and the application framework are based

on Unity and integrated as a component of a template scene in Unity. Finally, the application is compiled and exported to a target device. There are no details given regarding specific hardware used (Thies et al., 2019).

Together, the compiler and the application framework function as an AR engine, which takes a Business Process Model and further inputs and converts that to an AR/VR training application.

Yigitbas et al. (2021) present a VR authoring tool to allow the simple creation and execution of interactive VR scenes. For this purpose, they implemented a web-based tool called VREUD (VR End-User Development). Users can model a 3D VR scene by adding and modifying objects, interactions with objects and tasks. The tool also has the ability to directly show the scene in the interface. A generator then creates an interactive VR scene from the model and stores it. Subsequently, the scene can be exported and executed on a HMD. For the creation of the tool, JavaScript with React and Three.js has been used for the user interface and the A-Frame framework for the AR parts and the execution (Yigitbas et al., 2021).

The VREUD generator is therefore a VR engine, that takes user-constructed models and translates them to a VR environment.

Campos-López et al. (2023) propose a model-driven approach that is based on the definition of a domain metamodel to build AR applications. Their goal is for users to perform domain-specific modeling inside an AR environment (immersive modeling). The specification of an AR application is structured around a domain metamodel that is supplemented by models defining different parts of the application. These additional models have specifications regarding the AR representation of the metamodel elements (e.g., size, rotation and interactions). They also determine the anchoring mechanism of virtual objects on the real world. In order to execute the specified AR application, an AR application interpreter called *ALTER* (domAin modeLling using augmenTEd Reality) has been created. This tool, which runs as a native iOS app on phones and tablets, takes a domain metamodel created with the dedicated *ALTER* designer and executes it. Upon launching the tool, users have the option to either load a pre-existing model or initiate a new model from scratch by selecting an AR application specification. They can then start modeling and modifying inside the AR environment. *ALTER* is a native iOS application that uses Apples ARKit library and all of the AR models are represented as JSON documents. Interesting features of the application are anchoring virtual objects, scanning QR- and barcodes and the interaction with BLE beacons (Brunschwig et al., 2021; Campos-López et al., 2021; Campos-López et al., 2023).

Consequently, *ALTER* is an AR engine, which takes a domain metamodel and additional specifications and creates a domain-specific AR modeling environment.

The reviewed papers present various approaches to AR engines. Most systems consist of two main components: an authoring tool and a runtime engine that processes and executes AR content. A common trend is the use of XML-based formats to structure this content. However, similar to the authoring solutions discussed in Section 4.1.1, the software technologies used to implement these engines vary widely, as do the devices they run on. Also, the specific application domains differ and some engines are more automated, while others require additional manual development to complete AR applications. This highlights that there is no universal AR engine architecture and that solutions must be tailored to their specific use cases and requirements.

4.2 Engine of the AR Workflow Modeling Language

Initially implemented in ADOxx and now developed as a web application, the ARWFML enables users to graphically design various AR scenarios. The accompanying AR engine interprets the models created with the ARWFML and generates corresponding AR applications. The first engine version, designed for the ADOxx implementation, utilized XML files as input. The current version, tailored for the MM-AR, uses JSON files. Due to their similarities, this chapter focuses on the second and current version of the engine. Analogous to the MM-AR, it is implemented as a platform-independent web application and can be accessed through any compatible web browser on mobile devices (Muff & Fill, 2023a).

Following, we describe the technological stack and program components of the ARWFML’s AR engine, and evaluate its features. In the end, we showcase the engine using the previously introduced Lego example.

4.2.1 Technological Stack

The AR engine utilizes, among other technologies, the following to deliver its functionality:

- **Aurelia Framework**¹: Similar to Angular, Aurelia is a modern, open-source frontend framework designed to create single page applications. It supports TypeScript and offers a modular architecture, which simplifies the creation and management of dynamic user interfaces and enhances the overall maintainability of the application.
- **Three.js**: This is a powerful 3D JavaScript library and is employed to handle the rendering and manipulation of 3D models. Three.js provides the necessary tools to create animated and interactive 3D graphics, which in this case is used for generating augmentations and visualizing them within the AR scenarios.
- **WebXR**: The WebXR standard ensures the application can deliver immersive AR experiences across different devices, facilitating interaction with and access to AR and VR devices on the web, including sensors and display technologies. This guarantee of compatibility with WebXR-enabled browsers allows users to access the AR engine on various mobile devices, including smartphones and HMDs, thus fulfilling the specified requirement SR₁₁ from figure 3.2.

4.2.2 Components

To begin an AR experience, the engine processes the models chosen by the user and monitors the environment for relevant changes (Muff & Fill, 2023a). It then adapts the environment based on these changes and user interactions, following the specified workflows (Muff & Fill, 2023a). To achieve this conversion from model to AR application, the AR engine uses several interconnected software components, implemented as TypeScript classes, which are described below.

Parsing the JSON Models

As a basis for all other classes, the singleton class `GlobalDefinition` represents the underlying data structure, storing in its instance all of the information needed by the engine to generate the application. It has

¹<https://aurelia.io>

fields specifying the AR environment (e.g., Three.js scene, camera, and renderer) and the engine logic (e.g., list with state machines). Furthermore, data regarding the models is saved here, with fields for all the elements of the three modeltypes *ObjectSpace*, *Statechange*, and *FlowScene*. Examples are lists of detectables, augmentations, conditions, *Statechanges*, relations and variables for the start, end, and origin instances. After the user selects a JSON file to be imported (the models are stored separately inside one JSON file), it is read and the models get filtered by modeltype. Additionally, the data within each model is identified using UUIDs and then loaded into the fields of the `GlobalDefinition` class instance, referred to as the `globalObjectInstance`. Afterwards, three objects are created, each being an instance of their respective singleton class: `FlowSceneHelper`, `ObjectSpaceHelper`, and `StateChangeHelper`. Each class has all fields belonging to the respective modeltype elements and their attributes. Based on the loaded *FlowScene* model, the `FlowSceneHelper` object is set up by populating its fields with data from the `globalObjectInstance`. Subsequently, the *ObjectSpace* and *Statechanges* referenced in the *FlowScene* are set up in a similar manner. At this stage, the AR engine is done with the loading and parsing of the JSON file and its contents. All information of the visual models is now stored in three class instances, which serve as the foundation for generating state machines in the next step.

Creating State Machines

For the origin, conditions, and *Statechanges* present in the *FlowScene*, state machines are created. In the AR engine, the `StateMachine` class includes fields to reference the current element (origin, condition, or *Statechange*), the next element (condition or *Statechange*), and the next state machine. Furthermore, the state itself can be set to *active*, *inactive*, or *done*. State machines are generated for the origin, each condition, and each *Statechange* and are then linked together by referencing the next state machine(s) in each state machine. The state of the origin is set to *active*, all others to *inactive*, and all state machines are finally saved in a list in the `globalObjectInstance`. These state machines represent the workflow of the AR application and are executed step by step. As soon as the world origin is defined (by e.g., recognizing a marker), the origin state machine is set to *done* and the next state machine(s) to *active*. When a condition state machine is executed, the condition has to be met (e.g., timer or button press), for the next state machine to be activated. When a *Statechange* state machine is executed, the actions specified in the *Statechange* have to be performed (e.g., rotate, move, or toggle visibility of augmentations). When all of the state machines are set to *done*, the workflow of the modeled AR application has reached its end and there will be no changes to the augmentations.

Generating the AR Environment

Upon opening the AR engine, a Three.js scene utilizing a WebXR renderer is created, functioning as the AR environment. It is initialized with lights and the origin is set to the point with coordinates (0, 0, 0). Afterwards, an animation loop is created, which is called continuously while the program runs. The loop employs an image tracking handler that constantly monitors the users real world environment and adapts the augmentations based on user input and environmental changes, according to the specified workflow. As soon as a marker is detected, its reference is identified in the `globalObjectInstance`, and the appropriate action is carried out. If it is an origin marker, the origin gets updated to the position of the printed out marker. Recognizing a non origin marker belonging to a condition leads to the state machine of the condition to be set to *done*. The animation loop also calls a function to run the next *active* state machine(s), advancing the

workflow modeled in the *FlowScene*. The graphical information of the augmentations themselves (in the form of a 3D object, animation, image, video, audio, label, or link) is stored in the JSON file in text format. During the parsing of the JSON file, a Three.js 3D object is created and saved for each augmentation, making it easy to visualize and animate them during the execution of the AR application. These 3D objects are added to the Three.js scene following their individual specifications in the *Statechanges* and *FlowScene* models.

4.2.3 Limitations of First AR Engine Prototype

The AR engine created by Muff and Fill (2023a) is a prototype and thus does not encompass all the features and requirements enabled by the ARWFML. It is therefore important to evaluate the engine to determine its strengths and identify any gaps in the implementation, especially with respect to developing a new engine prototype.

The AR engine can be accessed through a WebXR-compatible browser on mobile devices such as phones and tablets. Once the engine is opened, users can import local JSON models created with the ARWFML and exported using the MM-AR. The workflow defined in the *FlowScene* model is then initiated, activating the device's passthrough mode, allowing users to view their real-world environment with digital augmentations superimposed. Marker detection works with printed markers that are referenced in the *ObjectSpace* model as images. Upon detecting the origin marker, the augmentations in the *Statechanges* are shown according to how they are modeled in the workflow. As for conditions, timer and marker detection have been implemented.

One of the major drawbacks of the engine is that it only runs on mobile devices and not on immersive Head-Mounted Displays. This limitation is primarily due to the restrictions of WebXR. Although the engine is accessible through browsers on HMDs, essential features are not supported. Image tracking, necessary for marker detection, is an experimental feature in WebXR and currently not supported on HMDs. The engine relies on markers to define a world origin and for the detection conditions. Without an origin, the AR application cannot run. Additionally, WebXR does not support object detection, which means the detection condition type only works with image references, with no capability to have 3D objects as detectables, as is intended by the MM-AR. Other condition types, such as clicking on augmentations or using voice commands, and the concept of adding observers to conditions, are technically feasible but have not yet been implemented.

In summary, the AR engine developed by Muff and Fill (2023a) offers basic features for generating AR applications on mobile devices using JSON models created with the MM-AR and ARWFML. Origin detection and the condition types timer and detection (using images) are implemented. The current scientific contribution of the AR authoring solution is primarily conceptual and can largely be attributed to the AR Workflow Modeling Language. The implementation itself, particularly the AR engine, does not yet support the full range of features provided by the modeling language and can further be extended and improved.

4.2.4 Example using a Handheld Device

In figure 4.1, screenshots of the AR engine developed by Muff and Fill (2023a) are displayed. Subfigures (a-f) show the engine running in a Chrome browser on an Android tablet. Subfigure (a) illustrates the user interface to upload and import models from local storage, which are then processed by following the steps

described in section 4.2.2. Once parsing is complete, the engine starts the AR application and activates passthrough via the device's camera. Subfigures (b) and (c) depict the user's environment, with the origin marker laying on the ground. To detect the marker, the user needs to get close to it, as shown in subfigure (c). When the origin is detected, the modeled workflow is initiated and executed. In the Lego example, the first *Statechange*, and thus the first stone, is set after one second on top of the origin (modeled in the *FlowScene* in figure 3.8), as seen in subfigure (d). The second and third stones are placed after five and three seconds, respectively, as shown in subfigures (e) and (f). The user can move around freely and reposition the device, with the augmentations remaining fixed with regard to the origin. The Lego example is a simple demonstration of the AR engine and encompasses the full process from importing models to executing the workflow. As described above, the engine works with basic features as intended.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Figure 4.1: AR Engine of the ARWFML: Lego Example. Screenshots showing the stages of the AR Engine from uploading models (a), detecting the origin (b, c), and displaying the three *Statechanges* of the workflow (d-f).

Chapter 5

Design Objectives and Requirements

This chapter outlines the design objectives and requirements for the solution, our new AR engine prototype. Together with the subsequent development chapter, it answers the second research question. The design objectives define the high-level goals and motivation behind the development of the solution. Furthermore, they provide a scope for the prototype and form the basis from which more specific and detailed requirements are derived. These requirements are later used to evaluate the implementation of the new AR engine prototype.

5.1 Design Objectives of the Solution

According to the procedure by Peffers et al. (2007), the objectives of a solution are inferred from both the problem definition and the knowledge of what is possible and feasible. Therefore, by using the problem definition as a foundation, along with an understanding of the modeling language (ARWFML), the modeling environment (MM-AR), and the accompanying AR engine, several design objectives have been derived. On one hand, they provide a clear vision of what the solution aims to achieve, and on the other hand, they limit the solution space of the prototype.

This thesis builds on the work done by Muff and Fill (2023a). More specifically, we are developing a new and different version of their web-based AR engine, which uses Three.js and WebXR. Both AR engines utilize models created with the ARWFML as their input. The concrete implementation of the ARWFML, and the conversion and export of the visual models to text format, is done in the MM-AR. Consequently, our solution relies not only on the existing AR engine, but also on the MM-AR and the ARWFML. These three parts together establish the constraints for our implementation, which are represented in the formulation of the following objectives. Table 5.1 provides a summary of the design objectives for implementing a new AR engine that generates AR applications from visual models. Each objective is numbered, has a name, as well as a concise description. Additionally, a distinction is made between different sources of the objectives: defined by the author, derived from the MM-AR, or derived from the existing AR engine. In the following, the design objectives are explained in detail.

The overarching goal of the AR engine prototype is to function as an extension to the MM-AR in the two part AR authoring solution proposed by Muff and Fill (2023a). Its main purpose is to improve the efficiency

No.	Name	Description	Source
DO ₁	AR Application Development	Develop a prototype that generates an AR application accessible to users.	Author
DO ₂	Model Compatibility	Ensure the prototype supports the importing of models created in the MM-AR with the ARWFML.	MM-AR
DO ₃	Immersive Device Support	Ensure the prototype runs on devices with immersive Head-Mounted Displays.	AR Engine
DO ₄	Diverse Technology Stack	Use a different set of technologies for the development and implementation of the prototype compared to the existing AR engine.	AR Engine
DO ₅	Enhanced Functionality	Add additional functionalities to the prototype beyond what the existing AR engine offers.	AR Engine

Table 5.1: Design Objectives of the Solution

of AR application development by automatically generating applications from visual models. This purpose is represented in the first two design objectives. The output of the AR engine prototype is a program that has the properties of an AR application (DO₁). For the definition of the properties, we use the characteristics defined by Azuma (1997): the AR system combines real and virtual elements, is interactive in real time, and registers virtual objects in three-dimensional space. The application not only has to be generated, users also have to be able to access, run, and use it (DO₁). Additionally, the AR engine prototype is compatible with the MM-AR (DO₂). In detail, visual models based on the ARWFML, created with the MM-AR, are imported in text format (DO₂). As the models need to be understood and parsed, the AR engine prototype must incorporate the metamodeling concepts of the ARWFML, and the concrete syntax of the language used in the MM-AR.

Since there already exists an AR engine, the new prototype not only has to significantly differ from it, but provide supplementary value as well. This value is not confined to the specific solution and its features, but also encompasses the process of creating the solution. The last three design objectives incorporate this distinction from the existing AR engine. The existing engine does not run on HMDs, which is a significant drawback to the authoring solution in general. The new engine prototype therefore needs to be compatible with HMDs (DO₃). Subsequently, the new engine prototype is not implemented as a web-based application with Three.js and WebXR, but instead employs a different technological stack, such as a different programming language and development platform (DO₄). This results in a completely new process for creating the engine prototype, as well as compatibility with a distinct set of devices. Rather than having a web application running on any mobile device with a WebXR-enabled browser (with limitations), the new engine prototype can be built specifically for one type of AR display or device. There are various advantages to this approach, with the most prominent being an optimized performance, and access to proprietary APIs and advanced features. This allows the new engine prototype to support functionality previously not available or possible in the existing AR engine (DO₅). In summary, the AR engine prototype differs in the way it is developed and implemented, and in the way the user experiences and interacts with it.

5.2 Requirements of the Solution

From the design objectives, requirements for the new AR engine are derived. A requirement is a documented condition or capability needed by a user or a system to solve a problem, achieve an objective, or comply with formal standards and specifications (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers, 1990). For the new AR engine, these requirements will define essential and advanced features and capabilities necessary to meet user needs and ensure system functionality.

There are various ways to classify requirements by type, with the most straightforward being the distinction between functional and non-functional requirements (Wiegiers & Beatty, 2013). Functional requirements specify what the system should do under certain conditions, detailing the tasks, operations, and behaviors it must perform. These include specific functionalities such as user interactions, data processing, and business processes that the system must support. Functional requirements are mostly defined from the user's perspective and are represented by the inputs to the software system, the operations it performs, and its expected outputs. Non-functional requirements, on the other hand, describe how the system should perform these tasks, focusing on attributes such as performance, usability, reliability, security, and scalability. They are more abstract and mostly defined from the perspective of the developer and the system. Non-functional requirements encompass a wide range of types, including quality, design, and implementation constraints, and external interface and environmental requirements (Wiegiers & Beatty, 2013).

Table 5.2 lists the relevant requirements for the implementation of the new AR engine, categorized accordingly by type into functional and non-functional requirements. Each requirement is numbered, has a name, as well as a concise description. Equal to the design objectives, a distinction is made between different sources of the requirements: defined by the author, derived from the MM-AR, or derived from the existing AR engine. Additionally, the requirements are mapped to the design objectives by assigning a specific objective to each one. This ensures a clear connection between desired functionalities and the overall design goals, while verifying that each requirement contributes effectively to the attainment of a design objective. All design objectives therefore need to be covered at least once by a requirement. In contrast to the design objectives, a more detailed description of each requirement is not provided.

The requirements have been specified by following methods and best practices in requirements engineering (Wiegiers & Beatty, 2013), like the *Recommended Practice for Software Requirements Specifications* by the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (1998). Starting with the design objectives, an analysis of the ARWFML, the MM-AR, the existing AR engine, and potential user needs has informed the requirements outlined in table 5.2. The development of the new AR engine prototype in chapter 6 is based on, and guided by, these requirements. They also form the foundation for the evaluation of the solution done in chapter 7.2.

No.	Name	Description	Source	DO
Functional Requirements				
Req ₁	Model Import	The user must be able to import models in JSON format.	MM-AR	DO ₂
Req ₂	Model Parsing	The engine must parse <i>ObjectSpace</i> , <i>Statechange</i> , and <i>FlowScene</i> JSON models from the MM-AR.	MM-AR	DO ₂
Req ₃	Full Model Support	The engine must support the parsing of all model elements existing in the MM-AR.	MM-AR	DO ₂
Req ₄	Model Validation	The engine must validate the JSON models against predefined schemas.	MM-AR	DO ₂
Req ₅	Model Conversion	The engine must convert augmentations of the JSON models into AR application components.	MM-AR	DO ₂
Req ₆	AR Scene Generation	The engine must generate AR scenes from converted model components.	MM-AR	DO ₁
Req ₇	Object Placement	The engine must position, scale, and orient 3D objects as specified in the models.	MM-AR	DO ₁
Req ₈	Workflow Control	The user must be able to start, pause, and stop the execution of the AR workflow.	Author	DO ₁
Req ₉	Marker Tracking	The engine must detect and track markers, both images and 3D objects.	Author	DO ₅
Req ₁₀	World Origin	The user must define a world origin by detecting a marker.	Author	DO ₂
Req ₁₁	Condition Types	The engine must support the execution of the MM-AR condition types: timer, click, detect, voice, observer.	MM-AR	DO ₅
Non-functional Requirements				
Req ₁₂	HMD Compatibility	The engine must be accessible on and compatible with immersive Head-Mounted Displays.	AR Engine	DO ₃
Req ₁₃	Development Environment	The engine should be developed using the Unity platform.	Author	DO ₄

Table 5.2: Requirements of the Solution

Chapter 6

Design and Development

Building on the objectives and requirements outlined in the previous chapter, we now turn our focus to the design and development of the artifact (Peppers et al., 2007), the AR engine prototype. To maintain a manageable scope for this thesis, we have decided against a full implementation similar to the existing AR engine by Muff and Fill (2023a). Specifically, the initial steps of importing and parsing the MM-AR JSON models and creating corresponding state machines from these models, as described in section 4.2.2, will not be included in our implementation. This concerns Req₁ to Req₇ listed in table 5.2. As further discussed in the evaluation in section 7.2, this gives possibility for future work to expand and enhance our AR engine prototype and cover additional requirements. Since dynamic generation of AR applications from models is not required, the emphasis of this work is on creating an experimental prototype that runs on a HMD and demonstrates a hard-coded use case. The unique concepts and processes involved in developing applications for HMDs, as opposed to handheld devices and web-based solutions, still need to be evaluated and considered.

In the first section, the design choices for the software environment and hardware device are explained. Next, the use case is introduced with models created in the MM-AR. Following this, the implementation details are provided, covering technical limitations and the system architecture, with the code structure and most important classes. The files mentioned in this chapter are available via Zenodo¹.

6.1 Design Considerations

The initial step towards the implementation of the AR engine prototype is to determine the software development approach and the execution device. Furthermore, it is important to understand the selected software and hardware environments for successfully implementing the artifact and establishing a foundation for the rest of this chapter. The sections below provide the reasoning for choosing each environment, along with a general introduction to the topic.

¹<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13731823>

6.1.1 Development Environment: Unity

The decision to use the Unity game engine and development platform has mostly been made based on the implementation of the current web-based AR engine with Three.js and WebXR. As this engine doesn't run on HMDs due to technological constraints, alternative approaches were explored. Other AR development environments include Apple's Xcode² with ARKit, Google's Android Studio³ with ARCore, both of which are primarily used for handheld devices. Xcode can also be used with the Apple Vision Pro HMD, but since it was only released recently, it is not considered an option for this thesis. This narrows the choice down to the two game engines Unity and Unreal Engine, both of which support all the prominent AR SDKs and offer tools for AR development.

Unity has been chosen over Unreal Engine primarily due to its support for AR development and its large ecosystem of assets and plugins. Both engines are quite similar in terms of capabilities, but Unity's interface and comprehensive documentation make it more accessible for rapid prototyping and iterative development. In contrast, while Unreal Engine is known for its high-fidelity graphics, it has a steeper learning curve and less extensive AR support.

Unity is a widely used game engine and development platform known for its versatility and extensive toolset. Unlike a standard integrated development environment (IDE), which primarily focuses on code editing and debugging, Unity provides tools for modeling in 3D, physics simulation, and real-time rendering. This allows developers to create 2D, 3D, VR, and AR applications across various platforms.

The **Scene** is the most fundamental building block in Unity (Unity Technologies, 2024). A Scene contains the environments and menus of the application. Everything in Unity is built around Scenes, which serve as containers for all the **GameObjects**. For example, in a game with multiple levels, each level would be represented as a separate Scene, allowing for distinct environments and gameplay elements within each level.

GameObjects are the entities within a Scene, representing characters, props, lights, cameras, or any other element of the game (Unity Technologies, 2024). Essentially, every object in a Unity application is a **GameObject**. **GameObjects** themselves do not have any inherent behavior, but their functionality is defined by attaching various **Components** to them.

Components are the functional pieces that define the behavior and appearance of **GameObjects** (Unity Technologies, 2024). Examples include **Transform** components for position and rotation, **Renderer** components for appearance, and **Collider** components for physical interactions.

Scripts contain the programming logic of the application (Unity Technologies, 2024). Written in C#, scripts allow developers to create custom behaviors by defining how **GameObjects** should interact with each other and respond to events within the Scene. Scripts are attached to **GameObjects** as components.

Assets are any external resources that are imported into a Unity project, such as textures, models, audio files, and prefabs (Unity Technologies, 2024). **Prefabs** are reusable **GameObjects** or collections of **GameObjects** that can be instantiated in multiple places within a Scene or across different Scenes.

All these elements - Scenes, **GameObjects**, **Components**, **Scripts**, and **Assets** - work together to create a straight-forward and interactive experience for AR development in Unity.

²<https://developer.apple.com/xcode>

³<https://developer.android.com/studio>

6.1.2 Device: Meta Quest 3 HMD

As for selecting a device, the choice had to be made between three available HMD options: Microsoft HoloLens, Meta Quest Pro⁴, and Meta Quest 3.

The Microsoft HoloLens offers AR capabilities with spatial mapping and enterprise-focused features, but it comes with a higher price tag and is primarily targeted towards industrial applications. The Meta Quest Pro, while providing enhanced performance and improved AR features, is also more expensive. In contrast, the Meta Quest 3, being the newest model, offers a balance of cost and performance. It is lighter and more compact than both the HoloLens and Meta Quest Pro, making it more comfortable for extended use. As an example, the video passthrough, essential for AR experiences, has seen significant improvements in video quality compared to the Meta Quest Pro. These advantages in cost, performance, and comfort make the Meta Quest 3 the most accessible and practical choice among the three devices.

The Meta Quest 3 utilizes two RGB color cameras with two LCD panels for video see-through, and integrates four infrared cameras to support controller and hand tracking, as well as room mapping (Meta, 2024). It also has two stereo speakers that enable spatial audio, as well as a microphone for voice input. Interaction with the device can also be achieved through hand tracking, utilizing finger and hand movements, or with the two controllers, each of which is equipped with multiple buttons, a joystick, and haptic feedback. The battery is integrated into the headset, making its use cordless (Meta, 2024).

6.1.3 Software Tool: Meta XR SDK

With the development platform and device selected, the next step was to choose an SDK that supports the Meta Quest 3 and integrates with Unity. There are three possible options available: Microsoft's Mixed Reality Toolkit (MRTK), the OpenXR standard in combination with Unity's AR Foundation framework, or the Meta XR SDK.

The MRTK was initially released to support the Microsoft HoloLens and has since evolved into an open-source project aimed at accelerating cross-platform AR and VR development in Unity. It is a comprehensive and robust SDK that supports a wide range of devices, while still maintaining a strong focus on the HoloLens. As for our considerations, the current version, MRTK3, offers only experimental support for Meta Quest devices (Microsoft, 2023). Given that the existing web-based AR engine is already constrained by the experimental features of WebXR, we preferred to avoid similar limitations and therefore did not consider MRTK any further.

OpenXR is an open standard developed by the Khronos Group⁵ for cross-platform AR and VR applications. When used in combination with Unity's AR Foundation framework, it provides a flexible and extensible approach to creating AR applications. OpenXR aims to enable interoperability between different hardware and software platforms, allowing applications to run on multiple devices without needing to rewrite code for each platform. This standardization promotes greater compatibility and reduces development overhead. Despite these benefits, there are some drawbacks to using OpenXR with Unity's AR Foundation. One of the primary issues is that the documentation for this combination is still insufficient, making it more challenging

⁴<https://www.meta.com/en/quest/quest-pro>

⁵<https://www.khronos.org>

to get up to speed and troubleshoot issues. Additionally, while OpenXR aims for broad compatibility, the integration with Meta Quest devices is not as seamless as it is with a dedicated device SDK.

The Meta XR SDK is specifically designed for the Meta Quest series and offers an optimized development experience for these devices. Originally created as part of Oculus’s ecosystem, the Meta XR SDK has evolved over time, benefiting from updates and refinements. It offers thorough documentation and a wide range of useful examples, which simplifies the development process. The resources and support available with the Meta XR SDK enable quick implementation of features and resolution of issues. Moreover, its integration with Meta Quest devices ensures optimal performance and compatibility. The SDK can be downloaded directly from the Unity Asset Store and imported into a Unity project via the Unity Package Manager, making setup straightforward and enabling rapid development and deployment of basic applications. A drawback of the Meta XR SDK’s focus on Meta devices is that it limits cross-platform support and compatibility, which can pose challenges if the goal is to target multiple AR or VR platforms and devices.

The objective of our AR engine is not to be compatible with as many devices as possible, but rather to serve as an experimental prototype that showcases the feasibility of the technology on a HMD. Comparing the OpenXR and Meta XR SDKs revealed that selecting the software tool which facilitates and accelerates the process of developing applications for the Meta Quest 3 in Unity is the most effective way to achieve our objective. We decided to use the Meta XR SDK, as it best aligns with these requirements.

6.2 ARGuide Use Case

To showcase the AR engine prototype and its features, a use case called ARGuide has been modeled in the MM-AR, which will be directly implemented into the engine. All model files of the ARGuide in JSON format are available via Zenodo⁶. The goal of this use case is to demonstrate both the basic and extended capabilities of the engine, such as displaying augmentations in form of *Statechanges* and the different conditions between them. The concept of ARGuide is to provide an AR-supported guided tour that leads visitors through a building, showing relevant information about the various locations and rooms. Users of ARGuide can walk into a building while carrying or wearing a compatible device and scan the origin marker located at a specific location in the building. Afterwards, a series of *Statechanges* and conditions will be launched. The *Statechanges* will display information to visitors in form of augmentations placed relative to the origin. Meanwhile, the conditions make it possible for the visitor to follow the tour and interact with the experience.

As a simple example, ARGuide has been modeled to lead a visitor through a corridor where three different groups of the same project could be located. The corridor has three doors, each leading to a room occupied by one of the groups. To provide visitors with information about each group, an information screen appears in front of each door, displaying the group’s name, a brief description, and a list of their current projects. To direct the visitor to the next door and information screen, a directional arrow pointing in the relevant direction is displayed.

Figure 6.1 - 6.5 show models of the ARGuide use case modeled in the MM-AR. The *ObjectSpace* in figure 6.1 consists of an origin marker, three two-dimensional room information screens, and one three-dimensional arrow. These augmentations are then referenced in six *Statechanges*, with the first, second, and last being

⁶<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13731823>

Figure 6.1: MM-AR *ObjectSpace*: ARGuide. Screenshot of the *ObjectSpace* model of the ARGuide, which encompasses one origin marker, and four augmentations: three for the room information screens and one for the directional arrow.

Figure 6.2: MM-AR *Statechange 1*: ARGuide. Screenshot of the *Statechange 1* model of the ARGuide, which displays the room 1 information screen in front of the first door. The point (0,0,0) of the coordinate system, which will be the origin, has also been edited into the screenshot.

Figure 6.3: MM-AR *Statechange 2*: ARGuide. Screenshot of the *Statechange 2* model of the ARGuide, which displays the arrow between room 1 and 2.

Figure 6.4: MM-AR *Statechange 6*: ARGuide. Screenshot of the *Statechange 6* model of the ARGuide, which displays all three of the room information screens in their correct position and rotation in the real corridor, relative to the origin.

Figure 6.5: MM-AR *FlowScene*: ARGuide. Screenshot of the *FlowScene* model showing the workflow of the ARGuide. It references the six *Statechanges* and has seven conditions with different condition types.

displayed in figure 6.2, 6.3, and 6.4 respectively. In figure 6.2, the point (0,0,0) of the coordinate system has been edited into the screenshot. During the execution of the application, the origin will serve as this point, from which the augmentations are positioned relatively. The augmentations in the *Statechanges* are positioned and rotated in three-dimensional space to match the layout and dimensions of the real corridor, while taking the placement of the origin into account. The *Statechanges* 1-6 encompass the following:

1. Room 1 information screen (figure 6.2)
2. Arrow between room 1 and 2 (figure 6.3)
3. Room 2 information screen
4. Arrow between room 2 and 3
5. Room 3 information screen
6. Room 1, 2, and 3 information screens (figure 6.4)

The *Statechanges* and the *ObjectSpace* are referenced in the workflow visible in the *FlowScene* model of figure 6.5. Additionally, seven conditions with different condition types are present. The workflow of ARGuide operates as follows: Five seconds after detecting the origin marker, the first information screen appears in front of the door to room 1. After ten seconds, the screen disappears, and an arrow pointing to the second door is displayed. The visitor can then click on the arrow to proceed with the tour, which causes the arrow to disappear and the information screen in front of room 2 to appear. When the visitor is ready, they can click on this information screen, making it disappear and revealing an arrow pointing to the third door. At this point, ARGuide waits for the visitor to say "next." Once recognized, the system advances to display the third information screen in front of room 3, while the arrow disappears. The visitor can say "next" again to reach the final *Statechange*, where all three information screens are shown simultaneously in front of their respective doors. The visitor can review any of the information screens and click on one to end the ARGuide.

The workflow described above includes three types of conditions: timer, click, and voice. For a timer condition, a specific duration is set, after which the condition is met and the next *Statechange* is triggered. In our case, the timers are set to five and ten seconds, respectively. The click condition requires the user to interact with one of the augmentations displayed in the previous *Statechange*. In the first and second click conditions, only one augmentation is present, so the user must click on that specific augmentation. Before the final click condition, there are three augmentations available, allowing the user to click on any of the three information screens to satisfy the condition. For a voice condition, a predefined cue word or phrase must be recognized to trigger the next *Statechange*. In our case, the user needs to say the cue word "next" to proceed.

These various condition types illustrate the different ways in how the user and the system interact with each other. The ARGuide use case can be further expanded by modeling additional rooms (such as lecture halls and classrooms) and incorporating other condition types.

As outlined in section 3.3, the MM-AR models are exported to JSON files, which can be imported by an AR engine to generate and run the ARGuide application. Since our engine prototype will not support the

dynamic importing and parsing of models, these MM-AR models are currently solely used for demonstration purposes and to aid in better understanding of the workflow. For now, the application will be directly implemented into the engine. In future work, once the AR engine prototype has been extended to enable importing and parsing of MM-AR files, these models will be all that is required to create the ARGuide application.

6.3 Implementation

After selecting the software and hardware environments, and modeling the ARGuide, the development of the AR engine prototype and the implementation of the use case can begin. The latest versions of Unity and the Meta XR SDK are used alongside Visual Studio Code⁷ for code editing. For testing, the application is compiled into an APK file, transferred to the Meta Quest 3 headset via a cable, and executed on the device. The source code of the Unity project and the APK file of the AR engine prototype are available via Zenodo⁸.

In the initial stages of development, some limitations associated with the Meta Quest headset became apparent, which is discussed in the following section. Subsequently, after a general overview of the system architecture is given, the most important classes of the engine prototype implementation are explained in further detail.

6.3.1 Technical Limitations

Two technical limitations, created by Meta’s software policies and privacy requirements, had to be considered during the implementation of the AR engine prototype. The first involves the play area boundary, and the second the access to the camera feed.

Boundary Limitations

The boundary system on Meta Quest headsets is a built-in safety feature that allows users to set up virtual walls, which appear when they approach the edges of their designated play area, helping prevent accidents. The boundary is particularly useful in VR experiences, where the user is fully immersed and unable to see their surroundings. In contrast, for AR applications, a boundary is generally less critical since the user can still perceive their real environment. However, since the Meta Horizon OS on Meta Quest devices does not differentiate between levels of immersion and always requires a boundary for AR applications to function, the Meta Quest 3 cannot be used outside of this mapped space. The play area is saved for the current environment, so it only needs to be reconfigured when the device is moved to a new location. Consequently, the boundary system limits the practicality of the engine prototype, particularly in the ARGuide use case, as each user must first set up a boundary by scanning the room before being able to start the engine prototype. As a result, the concept of visitors simply entering a building with a Meta Quest headset, scanning a marker, and receiving a guided tour remains an idea.

An effective solution would be to provide headsets on-site with a preconfigured boundary, allowing visitors to pick up the device at the entrance, much like an audio guide in a museum. This highlights another limitation

⁷<https://code.visualstudio.com>

⁸<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13731823>

of the boundary system: the maximum room size it can handle. The Meta Quest 3 is primarily designed for in-home and personal use, rather than for large spaces or buildings such as universities. Therefore, the boundary works well in smaller, apartment-sized rooms but faces difficulties in more expansive places and cannot be defined across multiple rooms. This makes the engine prototype with the ARGuide use case difficult to implement in its broader concept. However, for our specific ARGuide example presented in section 6.2, which is limited to a single corridor, the boundary is not an issue, though it must be defined before running the application.

The boundary system can fully be disabled for development purposes by putting the device into developer mode. While we utilized this feature during the implementation of the engine prototype and use case, it is not a viable option for broader public use of the AR engine. Additionally, when the boundary is deactivated in developer settings, passthrough is not displayed during screen capture, resulting in only the augmentations being visible against a black background.

The limitations of the boundary system do not directly affect our implementation of the engine prototype and ARGuide use case. However, since the final concept of the AR engine involves dynamically generating applications from a variety of models, the boundary system issue has to be addressed in any future work.

Camera Access Limitations

Due to user privacy and security concerns, Meta currently does not permit third-party developers to access camera data on Quest devices (the same restriction applies to Apple’s Vision Pro). While developers can use camera passthrough as a background, they cannot directly access the camera feed. Instead, they are provided with higher-level data such as hand and body skeletal coordinates, and spatial mapping of the environment. This restriction limits various AR capabilities, as developers are unable to run their own computer vision models, making optical detection and tracking of objects and markers impossible. Only hand and controller tracking are integrated into the Meta XR SDK, and a 3D mesh of the environment, including walls and furniture defined by the user, is accessible.

There are two possible workarounds for this issue, which would enable some sort of optical detection and tracking. The first is to attach an additional camera to the headset to capture optical data, which can then be processed by computer vision models to provide object and marker detection. The second is to use the streaming feature of the Meta Quest 3 to transmit the user’s view to an external computer, where a computer vision model can analyze the field of view by capturing the computer’s display. The results of this analysis can then be sent back to the AR engine running on the device. Both solutions have significant drawbacks, particularly in terms of latency issues, making them impractical for the purposes of this thesis. Therefore, they are not considered further.

The inability to access camera data has fundamental implications for the AR engine prototype: the modeling language ARWFML of the MM-AR relies on marker detection to set the origin and for the detectable condition type. Especially the definition of an origin is essential, as all augmentations in a modeled AR application are positioned relative to the origin in 3D space. The detectable condition type is not further discussed here, since for the prototype it can be replaced by other condition types and is not part of the ARGuide workflow. To establish the origin, we need to implement an alternative to the printed marker used in the AR engine by Muff and Fill (2023a). The simplest approach is to allow the user to set the origin with the Meta Quest 3 controllers. Using the SDK’s built-in controller tracking, the user can set the origin by holding down a button, moving the controller to the desired location, and then releasing the button to

finalize the origin placement before starting the workflow. This method doesn't require marker detection and is sufficient for a first implementation of the AR engine prototype.

6.3.2 System Architecture

This section provides an overview of the general system architecture and the Unity scene, script, and prefab components required for the AR engine prototype. The subsequent sections will describe the key elements in greater detail.

Scenes

The AR engine prototype is composed of four Unity scenes, each responsible for a different part of the application. The **menu scene** displays a welcome menu upon launching the engine, featuring a button to initiate the model "importing" process. In the final version of the engine, this would trigger a window allowing users to import MM-AR model files, which would then be parsed and converted into a state machine. In our prototype, however, the ARGuide use case is integrated directly into the engine, so no importing or parsing is required. Instead, the button in the menu scene loads the **import scene**, which confirms the successful "import" of models and proceeds to either the tutorial scene (if the tutorial has not been previously viewed) or directly to the application scene. The **tutorial scene** provides instructions on interacting with the application during workflow execution and includes a button to load the application scene. The **application scene** generates a state machine from the ARGuide model information, which is hardcoded into a script of the scene, as model importing is not utilized. Additionally, it manages the positioning of the origin and then executes the *FlowScene* by initiating the state machine. The application scene also handles user interactions with the engine for both click and voice conditions, as well as when the user chooses to exit the workflow and return to the menu.

Each scene has a camera `GameObject` configured for AR setups. This camera features a passthrough layer and adds controller tracking and interactions, increasing immersion and usability by overlaying virtual controllers onto the real ones. Additionally, the controllers have a light ray and a cursor, facilitating ray-based interactions.

Scripts

Written in *C#*, scripts and their classes can either be attached to a `GameObject` in a scene or utilized by other scripts. The engine includes a script for each scene, providing the functionality required for that specific scene. Additionally, there is a raycast script, which is added as a component to the augmentation prefabs, to manage clicks on the augmentations according to the click conditions. For the state machine and the model logic defined in the ARWFML and the MM-AR, additional classes have been defined, which are all utilized in the application script of the application scene. These include classes for the state machine and its elements, such as *Statechanges* and condition types, as well as a class for the origin.

Prefabs

Prefabs have been created for all the augmentations present in the ARGuide *ObjectSpace* model of figure 6.1. The prefabs for the information screens have been made directly in the Unity editor, with each screen having two versions: one that is non-clickable and another that is clickable. The clickable version includes

a collider and the raycast script. This distinction is needed because, depending on the workflow's condition types, some augmentations need to be interactive, while others should remain non-interactive. For the arrow augmentation the same two versions have been created. Additionally, a separate prefab has been developed to visualize the origin using a 3D coordinate system, featuring colored arrows as x-, y-, and z-axes.

6.3.3 Menu Scenes

The three scenes that include menus - the menu, import, and tutorial scenes - are nearly identical in their setup. Each scene has a ray-interactable canvas with text and a button, along with a script. The script ensures that the menu remains positioned and oriented in front of the user at a consistent distance, adjusting as the user moves their head to keep the menu within view. It also handles the button click and loads the next scene.

6.3.4 Origin Handling

As discussed in section 6.3.1, the origin of the workflow in the *FlowScene* is not defined by scanning a printed marker, but by placing it directly within the environment using the controllers. To facilitate this, an origin visualizer has been created, which shows the x-, y-, and z-axes in three dimensions, with the origin positioned at the intersection of these axes at the point (0,0,0). When the application scene is loaded, either after the tutorial or the import scene, the application script is executed, which handles everything regarding the origin. First, an origin visualizer `GameObject` is created, which the user can move by holding down the left-hand trigger button. The visualizer tracks the controller's movement, and when the button is released, it remains at the last position and rotation. If the origin is not moved for three seconds, it locks in place, and the visualizer disappears. The vector position and quaternion rotation are then stored in an instance of the `Origin` class, making them accessible to other classes. The `Origin` class only has two fields, one for position and one for rotation, along with a constructor. The `StateChange` class, in particular, relies on the origin information to display the augmentations of the *Statechanges* in relation to the origin. After the origin is locked and its position and rotation are saved, the rest of the workflow will be executed sequentially by activating the first element of the state machine.

6.3.5 State Machine and State Machine Element Classes

Although our engine prototype doesn't feature importing and parsing of models, it still makes sense to create a state machine for the execution of the workflow in the *FlowScene*, with conditions and *Statechanges* as its elements. To implement the state machine logic, the following classes have been created: `StateMachine`, `StateMachineElement`, `StateChange`, `PrefabInfo`, `Condition`, `TimerCondition`, `ClickCondition`, and `VoiceCondition`. The UML class diagram visible in figure 6.6 shows the interrelationships between these classes. The first two are discussed in this section, while the others are explained in the subsequent sections.

The `StateMachine` class represents a simple state machine used to manage transitions between different states in a workflow. It contains a field that references a `StateMachineElement` object, which represents the starting element and the initial state of the state machine, and it includes a corresponding constructor for initialization.

The `StateMachineElement` class is an abstract class, which serves as a base class for the elements in the state machine. There are two derived classes: `Condition` and `StateChange`. This class defines that each element has a type (`Condition` or `StateChange`), a current state (*inactive*, *active*, or *done*), and references to the previous and next elements in the state machine's workflow. The constructor initializes the state to *inactive*. The class also defines two virtual methods that can be overridden in the derived classes: one for activating the element (which sets the state to *active*) and another for deactivating the element (which sets the state to *done*). The state machine works by initializing each element present in the workflow of the *FlowScene* at the start of the application scene with information relevant for that element. All elements are then linked by adding references to the preceding and subsequent elements for each, ensuring that a `StateChange` always follows a `Condition`, and vice versa. The starting element in the state machine is activated first, triggering the subsequent elements sequentially until the workflow reaches its end. When a `StateChange` is active, its augmentations will be displayed. When a `Condition` is active, the workflow pauses until the condition is met. Elements that have been processed are set to *done*.

Figure 6.6: State Machine Implementation: UML Class Diagram (created by the author). `StateMachineElement` is an abstract base class for the `StateChange` and `Condition` classes. `StateMachine` references an instance of `StateMachineElement`. `PrefabInfo` is a nested class inside `StateChange`. `Condition` is an abstract base class for the three condition type classes `TimerCondition`, `ClickCondition`, and `VoiceCondition`.

6.3.6 State Change Class

The `StateChange` class is derived from the `StateMachineElement` class and represents a *Statechange* element in the state machine. It manages the instantiation and placement of augmentations - in the form of prefabs - in the scene according to the configuration of the *Statechange*. It also handles the deactivation of these prefabs. The class has a nested class `PrefabInfo`, which holds information about a prefab, including its `GameObject`, position, and rotation. Each `StateChange` object has a list of prefabs to be instantiated, represented as `PrefabInfo` objects, and a list of instantiated prefabs, represented as `GameObject` instances. A public method to add a prefab to the `StateChange` exists, taking a prefab, position, and rotation as parameters. When the `StateChange` element is activated by a previous state machine element, its state is set to *active*, then each prefab in the list (added by the method mentioned before) is instantiated using the

method `PlacePrefabRelativeToOrigin()`, and finally, the next state machine element is activated.

```
private void PlacePrefabRelativeToOrigin(GameObject prefab, Vector3 relativePosition, Quaternion relativeRotation)
{
    // Access the origin from the ApplicationScript
    ApplicationScript applicationScript = GameObject.FindObjectOfType<ApplicationScript>();
    Origin origin = applicationScript.GetOrigin();

    Vector3 originPosition = origin.Position;
    Quaternion originRotation = origin.Rotation;

    // Adjust the z-coordinate of relativePosition to match the orientation of the MM-AR
    relativePosition.z = -relativePosition.z;

    // Calculate the world position and rotation
    Vector3 worldPosition = originRotation * relativePosition + originPosition;
    Quaternion worldRotation = originRotation * relativeRotation;

    // Instantiate the prefab and add it to the list of instantiated prefabs
    instantiatedPrefabs.Add(GameObject.Instantiate(prefab, worldPosition, worldRotation));
}
```

Figure 6.7: `PlacePrefabRelativeToOrigin()` Method of the `StateChange` Class. This method instantiates a prefab relative to the current origin’s position and rotation, then adds the resulting `GameObject` to the list of instantiated prefabs. It is called for each augmentation of a *Statechange*, when the *Statechange* is activated.

The `PlacePrefabRelativeToOrigin()` method visible in figure 6.7 takes a `GameObject` prefab, a vector relative position, and a quaternion relative rotation as parameters. It then uses the origin information from the application script to calculate the world position and world rotation, with which the prefab is instantiated and made visible to the user. This method ensures that each augmentation is placed and rotated correctly relative to the origin, as defined in the *Statechange*. The instantiated `GameObject` is then added to the instantiated prefab list. As soon as the `StateChange` is deactivated (when the following condition of the workflow is met), its state is set to *done*, and each prefab in that list is destroyed, making it no longer visible to the user.

6.3.7 Condition Class

The abstract class `Condition` is a base class for condition elements in the state machine and is derived from `StateMachineElement`. The three condition type classes implemented in the engine prototype - `TimerCondition`, `ClickCondition`, and `VoiceCondition` - inherit from this class. The `ProcessCondition()` method visible in figure 6.8 is called by all three condition type classes as soon as the specified condition is met. This method processes the condition by deactivating the previous `StateChange` element, setting the current condition’s state to *done*, and activating the next `StateChange` element. If the condition doesn’t have a next element, the workflow has reached its end, and the import menu scene will be loaded.

6.3.8 Timer Condition Class

The `TimerCondition` class has the logic needed for the timer condition type and inherits from `Condition`. When a `TimerCondition` is activated, a coroutine is initiated, which waits for the duration specified for this timer and then processes the condition by calling the `ProcessCondition()` method of the `Condition` class.

```

protected void ProcessCondition()
{
    // Deactivate the previous state change element, if any
    if (PreviousElement is StateChange previousStateChange)
    {
        previousStateChange.Deactivate();
    }

    // Set the current condition's state to Done
    CurrentState = State.Done;

    // Activate the next element in the state machine (Statechange), if it exists
    if (NextElement != null)
    {
        NextElement.Activate();
    }
    else
    {
        // Load the "ImportScene" if there is no next element
        SceneManager.LoadScene("ImportScene");
    }
}

```

Figure 6.8: `ProcessCondition()` Method of the `Condition` Class. This method processes the condition by deactivating the previous `StateChange` element, marking the current condition as done, and activating the next element in the state machine. If there is no next element (end of workflow), it loads the import scene.

6.3.9 Click Condition Class

The `ClickCondition` class, together with methods defined in the application script, has the logic needed for the click condition type and inherits from `Condition`. A click occurs when the user of the engine clicks on one of the visible augmentations using the trigger button on either controller. The augmentation prefabs used for click conditions therefore need to be clickable. When a `ClickCondition` is activated, its state is set to *active*. The engine then waits for a click to be made on one of the prefabs added to the previous `StateChange` element. The application script has a method that is called by the prefab `GameObject` that was clicked on. When the method is called, the relevant active `ClickCondition` will be processed by calling the `ProcessCondition()` method of the `Condition` class.

6.3.10 Voice Condition Class

The `VoiceCondition` class, together with methods defined in the application script, has the logic needed for the voice condition type and inherits from `Condition`. A voice condition waits for the user to say a specific cue word or phrase and proceeds once the word or phrase is recognized by the microphone. Audio feedback has been implemented to notify the user when the microphone is active and listening, as well as when a correct word or phrase is recognized. To provide speech recognition, the Meta Voice SDK, powered by Wit.ai⁹, a natural language processing platform, is used. Each voice input is sent to Wit.ai for processing and comparison with pre-defined intents. The result of the analysis is sent back to the engine as either successful (intent has been recognized), or unsuccessful (a different intent or no intent at all has been recognized). Since the cue word of the ARGuide use case is "next", the *go forward* intent has been used, returning a

⁹<https://wit.ai>

successful recognition on words like "next". To handle the voice input and audio output, a `GameObject` for each has been created in the application scene. When a `VoiceCondition` is activated, its state is set to *active*, and a coroutine is initiated, which first plays a sound to indicate the activation of the microphone, and then activates the microphone. After sending microphone input to, and receiving the results from Wit.ai, one of two methods in the application script is called. For a successful recognition, the microphone is deactivated, and a sound to indicate the successful recognition is played. The relevant active `VoiceCondition` is then processed by calling the `ProcessCondition()` method of the `Condition` class. For an unsuccessful recognition, the microphone is reactivated again, giving the user another chance to say the correct word or phrase.

6.3.11 ARGuide State Machine Initialization

The ARGuide use case with all the information of the *FlowScene* model is directly implemented into the AR engine prototype. Upon starting the application scene and after the origin visualizer is initialized, the state machine for the ARGuide is set up using the `InitializeStateMachine()` method of the application script, as shown in figures 6.9 to 6.11. The `Condition` and `StateChange` elements are created independently and then linked together, and the state machine is initialized with the first condition as the starting element.

```
void InitializeStateMachine()
{
    // Create Condition elements with relevant information based on condition type
    Condition[] conditions = new Condition[]
    {
        new TimerCondition(5.0f, this),
        new TimerCondition(10.0f, this),
        new ClickCondition(),
        new ClickCondition(),
        new VoiceCondition(this)
        {
            audioSource = audioSource,
            micOnClip = micOnClip,
            recognizedClip = recognizedClip,
            appVoiceExperience = appVoiceExperience
        },
        new VoiceCondition(this)
        {
            audioSource = audioSource,
            micOnClip = micOnClip,
            recognizedClip = recognizedClip,
            appVoiceExperience = appVoiceExperience
        },
        new ClickCondition()
    };
};
```

Figure 6.9: `InitializeStateMachine()` Method of the Application Script: Conditions. This code snippet creates the `TimerCondition`, `ClickCondition`, and `VoiceCondition` elements of the ARGuide *FlowScene*, and adds relevant information to each. The elements are stored in an array.

Figure 6.9 shows the creation of the seven conditions with three different condition types. For the timer conditions, the duration of the timer is set, and a reference to the running application script is given, allowing the `TimerCondition` elements to pause the application by using a coroutine. The `ClickCondition` elements don't need any additional information. `VoiceCondition` elements also need a reference to the running application script to start coroutines which play sounds and activate/deactivate the microphone. Furthermore, since the `VoiceCondition` class is not added to a `GameObject`, it needs information about the

audio output and voice input GameObjects, as well as the sounds that need to be played. The `Condition` elements are stored in an array, facilitating the linking with the `StateChange` elements.

```
// Create StateChange elements
StateChange[] stateChanges = new StateChange[]
{
    new StateChange(),
    new StateChange(),
    new StateChange(),
    new StateChange(),
    new StateChange(),
    new StateChange()
};

// Add prefabs and position and rotation information to StateChange elements
stateChanges[0].AddPrefab(screen1Prefab, new Vector3(1.35f, 1.5f, -0.05f), Quaternion.Euler(0.0f, 0.0f, 0.0f));
stateChanges[1].AddPrefab(arrowPrefabRay, new Vector3(3.3f, 0.1f, 0.8f), Quaternion.Euler(0.0f, 0.0f, 0.0f));
stateChanges[2].AddPrefab(screen2PrefabRay, new Vector3(5.15f, 1.5f, 1.5f), Quaternion.Euler(0.0f, 180.0f, 0.0f));
stateChanges[3].AddPrefab(arrowPrefab, new Vector3(5.15f, 0.1f, 0.9f), Quaternion.Euler(0.0f, 270.0f, 0.0f));
stateChanges[4].AddPrefab(screen3Prefab, new Vector3(5.15f, 1.5f, -0.05f), Quaternion.Euler(0.0f, 0.0f, 0.0f));
stateChanges[5].AddPrefab(screen1PrefabRay, new Vector3(1.35f, 1.5f, 0.0f), Quaternion.Euler(0.0f, 0.0f, 0.0f));
stateChanges[5].AddPrefab(screen2PrefabRay, new Vector3(5.15f, 1.5f, 1.5f), Quaternion.Euler(0.0f, 180.0f, 0.0f));
stateChanges[5].AddPrefab(screen3PrefabRay, new Vector3(5.15f, 1.5f, -0.05f), Quaternion.Euler(0.0f, 0.0f, 0.0f));
```

Figure 6.10: `InitializeStateMachine()` Method of the Application Script: *Statechanges*. This code snippet creates the `StateChange` elements of the ARGuide *FlowScene* and stores them in an array. To each element, prefabs with their position and rotation information is added. The values are taken from the MM-AR and are relative to the origin.

Figure 6.10 shows the initialization of the six *Statechanges*. The `StateChange` elements are first created and stored in an array, facilitating the linking with the `Condition` elements. Furthermore, prefabs are added to each `StateChange` element, along with a vector position and quaternion rotation for that prefab. These position and rotation values are taken from the MM-AR *Statechange* models and are needed to position and rotate the augmentations in relation to the origin. The first five *Statechanges* each contain only one augmentation (either an information screen or an arrow), so only one prefab needs to be added to each element. The final *Statechange* displays all three information screens simultaneously, requiring all three prefabs to be added to its element. Prefabs for *Statechanges* preceding click conditions need to be clickable, which is why the ray-interactable versions of the prefabs are added to the second, third, and final `StateChange` elements.

Figure 6.11 shows the linking of the `Condition` and `StateChange` elements using two for-loops, as well as the initialization of the state machine. Each `Condition` references the previous and next `StateChange` element, ensuring that the first element's previous element and the last element's next element are set to null. Each `StateChange` references the previous and next `Condition` element. Finally, the state machine is initialized by adding the first condition as a starting element.

In the application scene, after the origin is placed and locked, the state machine is started by activating its starting element with `stateMachine.StartElement.Activate()`.

```

// Link each Condition element to its corresponding StateChange elements
for (int i = 0; i < conditions.Length; i++)
{
    if (i > 0)
    {
        conditions[i].PreviousElement = stateChanges[i - 1];
    }
    else
    {
        conditions[i].PreviousElement = null; // Ensure first element's PreviousElement is null
    }

    if (i < conditions.Length - 1)
    {
        conditions[i].NextElement = stateChanges[i];
    }
    else
    {
        conditions[i].NextElement = null; // Ensure last element's NextElement is null
    }
}

// Link each StateChange element to its corresponding Condition elements
for (int i = 0; i < stateChanges.Length; i++)
{
    stateChanges[i].PreviousElement = conditions[i];
    stateChanges[i].NextElement = conditions[i + 1];
}

// Initialize the state machine with the first condition as the starting element
stateMachine = new StateMachine(conditions[0]);
}

```

Figure 6.11: InitializeStateMachine() Method of the Application Script: Linking of Conditions and Statechanges. This code snippet links the Condition and StateChange elements, and initializes the state machine with the first condition as a starting element.

Chapter 7

Demonstration and Evaluation

Following the procedure proposed by Peffers et al. (2007), the first section of this chapter demonstrates the artifact created in this thesis: our implementation of the AR engine prototype with the included ARGuide use case. Afterwards, the third research question will be answered by evaluating the AR engine prototype. The evaluation is conducted by comparing the implementation with the requirements and design objectives established in chapter 5, which includes a comparison with the AR engine by Muff and Fill (2023a). We also discuss potential improvements and extensions to the engine prototype that are identified through the evaluation results.

7.1 Demonstration of the AR Engine Prototype

To demonstrate the AR engine prototype and the ARGuide use case implemented into it, screenshots showing the different stages of the application are provided in figures 7.1 to 7.12. The screenshots are taken from a screen recording made with the Meta Quest 3 HMD, which captures the user's field of view, microphone input, and speaker output. The complete video of the screen recording is available via Zenodo¹. The person is wearing the Meta Quest 3 headset and uses its two controllers in the corridor environment the ARGuide is modeled for. Before the AR engine prototype is executed, the user has to set up the play area boundary by either scanning the room or drawing it manually.

7.1.1 Menu Scenes

The screenshots in figures 7.1 to 7.3 show the three menus that are shown sequentially to the user when they open the application. Figure 7.1 presents the main menu corresponding to the menu scene implemented in Unity. It welcomes the user and provides a button to "import" models. The menus are always in front of the user, as they follow the head movement. Also visible in the screenshots are the controller overlays and the rays coming from them, which facilitate interaction. To push the button, the user can press either index trigger button when pointing with the ray to the button. This loads the import menu (import scene in Unity) visible in figure 7.2, which confirms the successful "importing" of the models. A button to start the workflow either

¹<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13731823>

Figure 7.1: AR Engine Prototype: Main Menu. Screenshot of the main menu screen that is shown to the user when starting the application. It welcomes the user and has a button which loads the import menu.

launches the tutorial menu or directly initiates the placement of the origin, depending on whether the user has seen the tutorial before. The tutorial menu (tutorial scene in Unity) in figure 7.3 shows instructions to the user on how to place the origin, interact with the workflow, and go back to the menu. When pressing the button to start the workflow, the application scene implemented in Unity is launched, enabling the placement of the origin and the execution of the workflow in the *FlowScene* model of the ARGuide.

7.1.2 Origin Placement

When the menus have been shown and the application scene implemented in Unity is loaded, the placement of the origin is initiated, visible in figures 7.4 to 7.6. The figures show the 3D coordinate system that is displayed to visualize the origin, which contains three arrows representing the x-, y-, and z-axes. The origin is the position at the intersection of these arrows. As long as the user presses the left-hand index trigger, the origin tracks the controller. This is shown in figure 7.4 and 7.5, where the user takes the origin and places it in the corner of the corridor. Releasing the trigger sets the origin at the current location, visible in figure 7.6, which gets locked after three seconds of not moving it again. The origin for the ARGuide use case is placed in the corner of the corridor. After the origin is locked, the workflow in the *FlowScene* of the ARGuide is started. The red and blue lines in figure 7.5 depict the predefined boundary of the play area that is only visualized when the user gets close to it.

7.1.3 ARGuide Workflow

After the origin is set and locked, the workflow of the ARGuide *FlowScene* model is executed, including its seven conditions and six *Statechanges*. Figures 7.7 to 7.12 show the augmentations of the six *Statechanges* in

Figure 7.2: AR Engine Prototype: Import Menu. Screenshot of the import menu screen that is shown after the main menu. It confirms the successful "importing" of models and has a button which loads the tutorial menu or initiates the placement of the origin.

Figure 7.3: AR Engine Prototype: Tutorial Menu. Screenshot of the tutorial menu screen that is shown after the import menu. It has instructions on how to place the origin, interact with the workflow, and go back to the menu. The button initiates the placement of the origin.

Figure 7.4: AR Engine Prototype: Origin Placement 1. Screenshot showing the origin tracking the left controller since the left-hand index trigger is pressed. Moving the controller moves the origin.

Figure 7.5: AR Engine Prototype: Origin Placement 2. Screenshot showing the origin tracking the left controller since the left-hand index trigger is pressed. The origin for the ARGuide use case is placed in the corner of the corridor. The red and blue lines depict the predefined boundary of the play area.

Figure 7.6: AR Engine Prototype: Origin Placement 3. Screenshot showing the origin no longer tracking the left controller since the left-hand index trigger was released. The origin is placed in the corner and will lock after three seconds, causing the origin visualizer to disappear and the workflow to start.

their respective world location. They are positioned and rotated relative to the origin, making it crucial to place the origin precisely to ensure a consistent repeated execution of the workflow.

The first condition is a timer of three seconds, after which the first information screen, visible in figure 7.7, is shown to the user in front of the first door. The second condition is a ten-second timer that controls how long the information screen is displayed before it disappears. After the information screen disappears, the first arrow guiding the user to the second door is visualized above the floor. The third condition is a click condition, requiring the user to click on the arrow by pointing the controller at it and pressing a trigger button to advance the workflow. After the arrow disappears, the second information screen is shown in front of the second door (figure 7.9). The fourth condition is also a click condition, where the user has to click on the information screen. Once this occurs, the information screen disappears, and the second arrow, guiding the user to the third door, is shown (figure 7.10). The following voice condition plays a sound to inform the user of microphone activation. It then waits for the user to say "next," and after recognizing the cue word, plays a sound to indicate correct voice input. The arrow then disappears, and the third information screen is shown in front of the third door. Another voice condition initiates the same process as just explained, and then the final *Statechange* is displayed, showing all three information screens in front of their respective doors at the same time (figure 7.12). The last click condition requires the user to click on one of the three screens, which ends the workflow and loads the menu, where the workflow can be started again.

At any point during the workflow, the user can press the menu button on the left controller to stop the process and return to the menu. When restarting the workflow, the origin must be set again, as it is not saved between executions.

Figure 7.7: AR Engine Prototype: ARGuide *Statechange 1*. Screenshot showing the first information screen in front of the first door, with information about the room and the project group that occupies it. When the origin is set and locked, the first condition (timer) waits for three seconds, after which this screen is displayed. Then, the second condition (timer) waits for ten seconds, after which this screen disappears again.

Figure 7.8: AR Engine Prototype: ARGuide *Statechange 2*. Screenshot showing the first arrow pointing from the first to the second door. It is displayed after the first screen disappears. The third condition (click) waits for the user to click on the arrow using the controller rays and a trigger button press, after which the arrow disappears.

Figure 7.9: AR Engine Prototype: ARGuide *Statechange* 3. Screenshot showing the second information screen in front of the second door. It is displayed after the first arrow disappears. The fourth condition (click) waits for the user to click on the information screen, after which the screen disappears.

Figure 7.10: AR Engine Prototype: ARGuide *Statechange* 4. Screenshot showing the second arrow pointing from the second to the third door. It is displayed after the second screen disappears. The fifth condition (voice) plays a sound to indicate the microphone activation and then waits for the user to say "next". When the cue word has been recognized, the arrow disappears.

Figure 7.11: AR Engine Prototype: ARGuide *Statechange* 5. Screenshot showing the third information screen in front of the third door. It is displayed after the second arrow disappears. The sixth condition (voice) plays a sound to indicate the microphone activation and then waits for the user to say "next". When the cue word has been recognized, the screen disappears.

Figure 7.12: AR Engine Prototype: ARGuide *Statechange* 6. Screenshot showing the corridor and all three information screens. It is displayed after the third screen disappears. The last condition (click) waits for the user to click on one of the information screens, after which the screens disappear and the menu is loaded.

7.2 Evaluation of the AR Engine Prototype

To evaluate the implementation of the AR engine prototype, we compare the final artifact against the requirements and design objectives established in chapter 5. This approach provides not only an overview of the application’s features, but also an analysis of areas for improvement and potential extensions in future work. Given that the design objectives (and consequently the requirements) reference the AR engine by Muff and Fill (2023a), the evaluation also includes a comparison to this initial engine. The first two sections provide an evaluation of each requirement and design objective, respectively. The final section discusses these evaluations and a general evaluation summarizing the most important aspects is given.

7.2.1 Evaluation of Requirements

Tables 7.1 to 7.13 present the evaluations of each requirement by comparing the AR engine prototype implementation against the requirements listed in table 5.2. For each requirement, the table provides its identifying number and name, along with an assessment of whether the requirement has been covered. The requirement can be classified as fully covered, partially covered, or not covered. Each evaluation includes an explanation of why the corresponding requirement is fully, partially, or not covered. Additionally, a comparison with the initial engine by Muff and Fill (2023a) is included, as well as suggestions for potential improvements to our implementation. These suggestions provide a starting point for additional work that can be done in the future.

Req ₁	Model Import	Covered:	No
Explanation: Is not covered since it was not part of the implementation focus. Instead, the information is taken from the models and directly hard-coded into the engine. Therefore, only the ARGuide use case can be generated with the engine.			
Comparison with initial engine: The initial engine supports model import.			
Improvements: This requirement can be covered by implementing a menu window that allows users to select and import their local model files, making it possible to dynamically generate any AR application modeled in the MM-AR.			

Table 7.1: Evaluation of Req₁: Model Import

Req ₂	Model Parsing	Covered:	No
Explanation: Is not covered since it was not part of the implementation focus. Instead, the information of the models is hard-coded into the engine by creating a state machine that has the condition and <i>Statechange</i> elements of the <i>FlowScene</i> model of the ARGuide use case.			
Comparison with initial engine: The initial engine supports model parsing of the three model types <i>ObjectSpace</i> , <i>Statechange</i> , and <i>FlowScene</i> .			
Improvements: This requirement can be covered by implementing a parser that reads the imported <i>ObjectSpace</i> , <i>Statechange</i> , and <i>FlowScene</i> models, extracts the information, and stores it in a suitable format.			

Table 7.2: Evaluation of Req₂: Model Parsing

Req ₃	Full Model Support	Covered:	No
Explanation: Is not covered since there is no model parsing at all.			
Comparison with initial engine: The initial engine only has partial model support since some model elements, specifically various condition types, are not implemented.			
Improvements: This requirement can be covered by first implementing a parser and then making sure to support all possible model elements including all condition types.			

Table 7.3: Evaluation of Req₃: Full Model Support

Req ₄	Model Validation	Covered:	No
Explanation: Is not covered since it was not part of the implementation focus.			
Comparison with initial engine: The initial engine supports model validation implicitly during the parsing process, as the model logic of the ARWFML and MM-AR is used to store the information.			
Improvements: This requirement can be covered by implementing a parser that also validates the models during the parsing process. Consequentially, the model logic of the ARWFML and the MM-AR needs to be implemented as well.			

Table 7.4: Evaluation of Req₄: Model Validation

Req ₅	Model Conversion	Covered:	No
Explanation: Is not covered since it was not part of the implementation focus. Instead, AR application components for the augmentations in form of Unity GameObject prefabs were created during the development process and are stored directly in the engine.			
Comparison with initial engine: The initial engine supports model conversion.			
Improvements: This requirement can be covered by implementing a parser that also converts the textual JSON information of augmentations into Unity GameObjects in order to visualize them to the user.			

Table 7.5: Evaluation of Req₅: Model Conversion

Req ₆	AR Scene Generation	Covered:	Partly
Explanation: Is partly covered since AR scenes in form of <i>Statechanges</i> are generated not from converted model components, but by using the already created GameObject augmentation prefabs.			
Comparison with initial engine: The initial engine supports AR scene generation from model components.			
Improvements: This requirement can be covered fully by first implementing model import, parsing, and conversion, and then making the <i>Statechanges</i> utilize the converted model components as augmentations instead of the pre-created prefabs.			

Table 7.6: Evaluation of Req₆: AR Scene Generation

Req ₇	Object Placement	Covered:	Partly
Explanation: Is partly covered since the augmentations in form of 3D objects are positioned and rotated, but not scaled, as specified in the MM-AR models. The position and rotation information is also not taken from imported models directly by the engine, but rather specified in the code in advance.			
Comparison with initial engine: The initial engine supports object placement.			
Improvements: This requirement can be covered fully by first implementing model import parsing, and then making the <i>Statechanges</i> utilize the position, rotation, and scale information to place the augmentations in the environment.			

Table 7.7: Evaluation of Req₇: Object Placement

Req ₈	Workflow Control	Covered:	Partly
Explanation: Is partly covered since the engine makes it possible for the user to start the workflow from the menu, and stop it at anytime, but not to pause it.			
Comparison with initial engine: The initial engine supports workflow control partly by enabling the user to start and stop the workflow, but not to pause it.			
Improvements: This requirement can be covered fully by mapping a button on the controllers to pause the application. When activated, this will temporarily pause the workflow’s execution, allowing the user to resume it later from the same point. This can be achieved by either utilizing coroutines, or by saving the current workflow execution process.			

Table 7.8: Evaluation of Req₈: Workflow Control

Req ₉	Marker Tracking	Covered:	No
Explanation: Is not covered since Meta’s policies don’t allow camera access for developers, making marker tracking impossible to implement.			
Comparison with initial engine: The initial engine supports marker tracking partly, since images, but no 3D objects can be tracked with it, due to technical limitations of WebXR.			
Improvements: This requirement can be covered by implementing one of the two workarounds described in section 6.3.1: attaching an external camera or analyzing the video stream on an external device. Alternatively, different hardware that supports marker tracking for developers could be chosen, which would necessitate rewriting large portions of the application code to run on a new platform.			

Table 7.9: Evaluation of Req₉: Marker Tracking

Req ₁₀	World Origin	Covered:	Partly
Explanation: Is partly covered since the user is able to define a world origin, but not by detecting a marker. Instead, the origin is placed manually in the environment by using a controller and moving it to the desired location.			
Comparison with initial engine: The initial engine supports the definition of a world origin by scanning a marker.			
Improvements: This requirement can be covered fully only by first enabling marker tracking (see table 7.9), and then replacing the controller placement method with a marker placement method. This would address a drawback of the controller placement method, ensuring consistency across different executions of the workflow.			

Table 7.10: Evaluation of Req₁₀: World Origin

Req ₁₁	Condition Types	Covered:	Partly
Explanation: Is partly covered since the condition types timer, click, and voice are implemented and can be executed, but not the detect and observer types.			
Comparison with initial engine: The initial engine supports only the condition types timer and detect with images.			
Improvements: This requirement can be covered fully by implementing the two condition types detect and observer. To enable 3D object and image detection as a condition, marker tracking must be activated first (see table 7.9). The observer condition type can be developed by adding additional conditional parameters and implementing the specific observer call (e.g., to a temperature sensor) along with the corresponding result handling.			

Table 7.11: Evaluation of Req₁₁: Condition Types

Req ₁₂	HMD Compatibility	Covered:	Yes
Explanation: Is covered since the AR engine is accessible and executable on the Meta Quest 3 HMD.			
Comparison with initial engine: The initial engine is accessible and executable on mobile devices having a WebXR supported browser.			
Improvements: Expanding compatibility to additional HMD devices would enhance the engine's accessibility. While the engine should run on other Meta Quest devices with minimal modifications (has not been tested), adapting it for other headsets would require significant development effort due to the need to utilize a different SDK.			

Table 7.12: Evaluation of Req₁₂: HMD Compatibility

Req ₁₃	Development Environment	Covered:	Yes
Explanation: Is covered since the AR engine has been developed with the Unity game engine and development platform.			
Comparison with initial engine: The initial engine has been developed with the Aurelia Framework, Three.js, and WebXR.			
Improvements: -			

Table 7.13: Evaluation of Req₁₃: Development Environment

7.2.2 Evaluation of Design Objectives

Since the requirements are derived from the design objectives, covering all the requirements in the implementation ensures that all design objectives are also achieved. In our case, the requirements outline a complete AR engine, which has not been fully realized. Therefore, an evaluation of the design objectives is also provided to determine whether they have been achieved. Tables 7.14 to 7.18 present the evaluations of each design objective by comparing the AR engine prototype implementation against the design objectives listed in table 5.1. For each design objective, the table provides its identifying number and name, along with an assessment of whether the design objective has been achieved or not. Each evaluation includes an explanation of why the corresponding design objective is achieved or not.

DO ₁	AR Application Development	Achieved:	Yes
<p>Explanation: This design objective was achieved, since the engine generates an AR application called ARGuide that fulfills the characteristics defined by Azuma (1997): it combines real and virtual elements, is interactive in real time, and registers virtual objects in three-dimensional space. Furthermore, the engine and the generated ARGuide application workflow is accessible to users on consumer-available devices.</p>			

Table 7.14: Evaluation of DO₁: AR Application Development

DO ₂	Model Compatibility	Achieved:	No
<p>Explanation: This design objective was not achieved, since the functionality to import models created in the MM-AR with the ARWFML has not been implemented. Because AR applications are not dynamically generated from models, there is no link between the modeling platform and the engine. Instead, an ARGuide use case has been modeled in the MM-AR, whose information was then hard-coded into the engine.</p>			

Table 7.15: Evaluation of DO₂: Model Compatibility

DO ₃	Immersive Device Support	Achieved:	Yes
<p>Explanation: This design objective was achieved, since the engine runs on the Meta Quest 3, which is an immersive HMD.</p>			

Table 7.16: Evaluation of DO₃: Immersive Device Support

7.2.3 General Evaluation

Reviewing the evaluations in the previous sections of the requirements and design objectives, it is noticeable that a majority of the requirements have either not or only partially been covered. The requirements specified in chapter 5.2 are not just a description of what is feasible within the context of this thesis, they rather define the features of a fully functional AR engine running on a HMD. Such an engine would import and parse the JSON models of the MM-AR, and dynamically generate an AR application displaying the specific workflow. The origin would be placed by scanning a marker, and all model elements, particularly all condition types as defined in the ARWFML (Muff & Fill, 2023a), would be fully supported.

DO ₄	Diverse Technology Stack	Achieved:	Yes
Explanation: This design objective was achieved, since the engine has been developed and implemented with a different set of technologies (Unity, Meta XR SDK) compared to the previous engine (Aurelia, Three.js, WebXR).			

Table 7.17: Evaluation of DO₄: Diverse Technology Stack

DO ₅	Enhanced Functionality	Achieved:	Yes
Explanation: This design objective was achieved, since the engine includes additional functionalities compared to the previous engine. Specifically, it introduces two new condition types - click and voice - which enhance user interaction with the engine and the workflow. Users can now interact by clicking on an augmentation or by speaking a cue word or phrase.			

Table 7.18: Evaluation of DO₅: Enhanced Functionality

The goal of this thesis is to focus on implementing an engine prototype that, in contrast to the initial engine, runs on a HMD and has some new functionality. This vision of what our thesis and artifact aims to achieve is represented in the design objectives, from which the requirements are derived. Therefore, in contrast to the requirements, four out of five design objectives have been achieved. Below is an analysis of the evaluations, highlighting the most important strengths and weaknesses of our AR engine implementation.

Strengths

Our solution primarily improves upon two areas: compatibility with HMDs (DO₃ and DO₄; Req₁₂ and Req₁₃) and the support of new conditions (DO₅; Req₁₁). Unlike the initial web-based engine, our development process utilized different technologies, making the engine compatible with HMDs, specifically the Meta Quest 3. Users can now wear a headset instead of holding a phone or tablet, resulting in a more immersive and hands-free experience. Interaction with the engine and workflow is facilitated through the intuitive Meta Quest 3 controllers, rather than a touchscreen, further enhancing usability and immersion.

Additionally, support for two new condition types has been added. Beyond timers, the workflow can now be advanced by clicking on augmentations or by saying a cue word. This allows users to create more varied AR workflows and extends the functionality of the MM-AR. Click and voice conditions are particularly useful when the user prefers to advance the workflow manually, rather than relying on automatic progression via timer or observer conditions. As demonstrated in the ARGuide, these conditions are ideal for scenarios where the user needs time to read or understand something, which can vary for each person.

Weaknesses

Deficiencies of our solution result either from time and scope constraints of the thesis or from technical limitations. As discussed in section 6.3.1, the boundary must be defined by the user before launching the AR engine on the Meta Quest 3. While this poses no issue for the ARGuide use case, where the environment is limited to a corridor that can be quickly scanned, other AR workflows spanning multiple rooms or floors would face challenges with the boundary system and the need to define it before executing an application.

One of the biggest limitations of using Meta Quest headsets is the inability to access camera sensor information, making native marker tracking impossible (Req₉). This impacts both the setting of the origin

(Req₁₀) and the implementation of detect conditions (Req₁₁), which advance the workflow by scanning an image or 3D object marker. As a result, detect conditions have not been implemented and are therefore unavailable to the user in our solution.

Setting the origin is crucial, as augmentations from the *Statechanges* are positioned relative to it. While our workaround allows users to position and rotate the origin with the left-hand controller, it has its drawbacks. An origin detectable marker can be fixed to the floor, wall, or another object, ensuring consistent placement across different workflow executions. However, with the controller method, the origin’s position and rotation vary with each execution, making it impossible to achieve identical placement every time. This inconsistency can lead to an unreliable or even unusable AR experience, particularly when precise augmentation placement is needed. For example, in the ARGuide, information screens should appear just slightly in front of each door and not in or behind the door. Rotation of the origin is particularly problematic, as even a small variation can result in augmentations being significantly displaced, especially as the distance from the origin increases. A turn of a few degrees of the origin could cause an augmentation several meters away to be positioned half a meter off from the desired location.

To address this issue, marker tracking could be implemented by either attaching an external camera or utilizing the video stream feature of the Meta Quest 3 and analyzing the feed on an external device. Alternatively, a different HMD that supports marker tracking for developers could be used, though this would require rewriting large portions of the application code to run on a new platform. As a temporary solution, a contraption could be built to hold the controller in place. This contraption could be fixed in place like a marker, allowing for consistent origin placement.

The most crucial feature that was not implemented due to the scope constraints of this thesis is the importing of MM-AR models (DO₂; Req₁ to Req₇). For demonstration purposes, a use case was directly implemented into the engine, limiting it to executing only the ARGuide workflow. As a result, our engine does not support the dynamic generation of AR applications from model files and there is no direct connection to the MM-AR. The authoring solution proposed by Muff and Fill (2023a) encompassing a modeling language and modeling platform to create models, and an AR engine to generate applications from the models, is not achieved. Implementing MM-AR model import and parsing for the three model types *ObjectSpace*, *Statechange*, and *FlowScene*, and enabling dynamic generation of AR workflows would bring the most significant improvement to the engine prototype. Therefore, any future work should prioritize addressing these requirements.

There are several functionalities of our solution that have either not been implemented or could be improved. These include:

- Implementing the observer condition type (Req₁₁).
- Improving the voice condition type to support specific cue words or phrases. Currently, only the cue word “next” is available for all voice conditions (Req₁₁).
- Improving object placement to not only position and rotate the augmentations as defined in the models, but to scale them as well (Req₇).
- Improving workflow control to allow the user not only to start and stop the workflow, but to pause it as well (Req₈).

- Improving user interaction by integrating hand tracking and gesture controls, which eliminates the need for controllers and makes the experience hands-free.

The improvements to the engine prototype listed above are technically feasible and may serve, together with the functionality to import MM-AR models, as a starting point for any future work.

Chapter 8

Discussion and Outlook

This thesis builds upon the work of Muff and Fill (2023a), enhancing their AR authoring solution by introducing a new AR engine prototype. This new engine addresses the problem of device compatibility faced by the initial engine, as it is accessible on Head-Mounted Displays. The research presented in this thesis is guided by the three research questions outlined in chapter 1.

To address the first research question, a comprehensive literature review was conducted to analyze the current state of the art technologies for developing dynamic, model-based AR applications. The result of the analysis shows, that various model-based AR authoring solutions exist, with each utilizing a different set of hardware and software technologies to achieve their specific goals. Some of these projects propose AR engines that are conceptually similar to the implementation of Muff and Fill (2023a), although none use the same technology stack as their web-based engine.

The second research question addresses how an Augmented Reality engine for the execution of dynamic, model-based Augmented Reality workflows can look like. Based on insights gained from the literature review and an analysis of the existing AR engine, five design objectives and 13 requirements have been specified. They describe an AR engine in the context of this thesis and the authoring solution by Muff and Fill (2023a), which also incorporates the modeling language (ARWFML) and the modeling platform (MM-AR). The key objectives for implementing the solution are ensuring compatibility with devices that have a HMD, incorporating additional functionality not present in the initial engine, and the dynamic importing of models created with the MM-AR. Following the design objectives and requirements, a new AR engine prototype was developed using the Unity development platform.

An evaluation of the engine prototype was conducted to address the third research question. To achieve this, the prototype's implementation was compared against each requirement and design objective, including a comparison with the initial engine. The evaluation results show that four out of the five design objectives, and therefore the main goals of our solution, have been achieved by the AR engine prototype. The engine is accessible on the Meta Quest 3 headset, demonstrating the feasibility of creating an AR engine for immersive HMDs. Users of the AR engine experience a more immersive and hands-free interaction compared to holding a phone or tablet. Furthermore, in addition to the timer condition type, two new condition types envisioned by the ARWFML have been implemented. Users can now also advance the workflow by clicking on the augmentations in their view or by saying a cue word, enabling the creation of different workflows for a more varied user experience. Compared to the initial engine, these two improvements enhance the

authoring solution of Muff and Fill (2023a), increasing both the accessibility and functionality of the AR engine component.

The evaluation results also highlight the limitations of the AR engine prototype's implementation. These limitations are either technical or due to scope constraints. The most significant technical limitation is the inability to use image or marker tracking when developing for Meta Quest devices. Since an essential part of the ARWFML logic involves defining a world origin by scanning a marker, a different process was implemented, allowing the user to set the origin manually using the Meta Quest 3 controllers. Compared to the marker-based approach used in the initial AR engine, this method is less consistent and can result in displaced augmentations. Additionally, the condition type relying on marker detection could not be implemented at all.

The most critical feature not implemented due to scope constraints is the importing of MM-AR models and the dynamic generation of AR application workflows from these models. In contrast to the initial engine, there is no direct connection to the MM-AR and as a result, the full integration of the model-based AR authoring solution proposed by Muff and Fill (2023a) could not be achieved. Instead, a use case called ARGuide was modeled with the MM-AR and then directly coded into the AR engine prototype to demonstrate its capabilities.

Future research and work on the AR engine component of the AR authoring solution by Muff and Fill (2023a) can proceed in two directions. One approach is to develop a new AR engine using different technologies to overcome the limitations of our implementation. The primary goal following this approach should be to select an HMD device and software environment that support marker tracking. Both the initial engine and our implementation are constrained by experimental feature support or privacy policies that restrict marker tracking on HMDs. The requirements specified in this work can be generalized to describe an AR engine regardless of the technologies used. They can therefore be adapted and applied when developing a new engine.

Alternatively, the AR engine prototype proposed in this thesis can be improved and further developed to more fully realize the features envisioned by the ARWFML. This approach should focus on developing functionality to import and parse MM-AR models, enabling dynamic generation of AR applications from these models. Additionally, attention should be given to addressing the marker tracking limitations. This can be achieved either by implementing a workaround to enable marker tracking, which would allow for origin definition using markers and make detection conditions possible, or by improving the controller origin placement method. The requirements and their evaluations can directly guide the further development of the AR engine prototype. Requirements that were not fully addressed, including those related to importing, parsing, tracking, and the origin, among others, can be further explored in addition to those already covered by the AR engine prototype implemented in this work.

The practical contribution of this thesis is an AR engine prototype that is compatible with and accessible on an immersive HMD, and enhances the functionality of the existing engine by two condition types. It integrates into the conceptual modeling approach for creating AR software applications proposed by Muff and Fill (2023a), which encompasses a modeling language, a modeling platform, and an AR engine. The capabilities of the AR engine prototype are demonstrated through a use case.

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